

ECCENTRIC BLACK HOLE GRAVITATIONAL-WAVE CAPTURE SOURCES IN GALACTIC NUCLEI: DISTRIBUTION OF BINARY PARAMETERS

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ABSTRACT

Mergers of binary black holes on eccentric orbits are among the targets for second generation ground-based gravitational-wave detectors. These sources may commonly form in galactic nuclei due to gravitational-wave emission during close flyby events of single objects. We determine the distributions of initial orbital parameters for a population of these gravitational-wave sources. Our results show that the initial dimensionless pericenter distance systematically decreases with the binary component masses and the mass of the central supermassive black hole, and its distribution depend sensitively on the highest possible black hole mass in the nuclear star cluster. For a multi-mass black hole population with masses between $5M_{\odot}$ and $80M_{\odot}$, more than $\sim 40\%$ of sources have an eccentricity greater than 0.1 when the gravitational-wave signal reaches 10Hz or if it forms at higher frequencies, but only $\sim 7\%$ of the sources with binary component masses less than $30M_{\odot}$ remain eccentric at this level near the last stable orbit (LSO). The eccentricity at LSO is typically between 0.005–0.05 for the lower mass BHs, and 0.1–0.2 for the highest mass BHs. Thus, due to the limited low-frequency sensitivity, the currently known six quasicircular LIGO/Virgo sources are compatible with this originally highly eccentric source population. At the design sensitivity of these instruments, the measurement of the eccentricity and mass distribution of merger events may be a useful diagnostic to distinguish among different astrophysical binary formation channels.

Keywords: black-hole physics – gravitational waves – galaxies: kinetics and dynamics – galaxies: nuclei – galaxies: clusters: general

1. INTRODUCTION

The Advanced Laser Interferometer Gravitational-wave (GW) Observatory¹ (aLIGO) (Aasi et al. 2015) and Advanced Virgo² (AdV) (Acernese et al. 2015) have made the first six detections of GWs (Abbott et al. 2016b,c, 2017a,b,c; The LIGO Scientific Collaboration et al. 2017) during the first two observing runs, and opened a new window through which the Universe can be observed. Two additional GW detectors are planned to join the network of aLIGO and AdV: (i) the Japanese KAGRA³ is under construction with baseline operations beginning in 2018 (Somiya 2012); while (ii) the proposed LIGO-India⁴ is expected to become operational in 2022 (Iyer et al. 2011; Abbott et al. 2016d). These instruments are expected to continue to make detections of GWs and to answer fundamental questions about their astrophysical sources.

One of the most anticipated type of events to be detected with ground-based GW detectors are the circular inspiral and coalescence of compact binaries consisting of neutron stars (NSs) and/or black holes (BHs). The current detections constrain the merger rate density of BH-BH mergers in the Universe to $12 - 213 \text{ Gpc}^{-3} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ (Abbott et al. 2017a). For a typical 2Gpc detection range for aLIGO's design sensitivity, this corresponds to a detection rate between $400 - 7,000 \text{ yr}^{-1}$. There are various theoretical studies to explain these rates (see Abadie et al. (2010) for a summary, and Dominik et al. 2013; Kinugawa et al. 2014; Abbott et al. 2016e,f; Belczynski et al. 2016; Rodriguez et al. 2016a; Sasaki et al. 2016; Bartos et al. 2017; Hoang et al. 2017; McKernan et al. 2017; Stone et al. 2017 and references therein for recent rate estimates). Since

GW emission tends to circularize the orbit as it shrinks the binary separation (Peters 1964), many of the GW sources are expected to have small orbital eccentricity by the time they enter the frequency bands of ground based GW detectors. For example, although the eccentricity of the Hulse-Taylor pulsar is currently 0.6171 (Hulse & Taylor 1975) it will have an eccentricity of $\sim 10^{-4}$ when it enters the aLIGO band (see Section 5.2). However, not all binary sources may be circular.

There are multiple reasons to expect a non-negligible eccentricity for some binary sources emitting GWs in the aLIGO band. One mechanism, which leads to eccentric mergers, is the Kozai-Lidov oscillations in hierarchical triple systems (Wen 2003), in which the binary is perturbed by a distant third object. Indeed, high mass stars, the progenitors of BHs, are commonly found in triples in the galactic field (i.e. more than 25% of massive stars are in triples Sana et al. 2014). Further, BH binaries can capture triple companions by dynamical encounters in dense stellar systems such as globular clusters (Wen 2003; Thompson 2011; Aarseth 2012; Antonini et al. 2014, 2016; Breivik et al. 2016; Rodriguez et al. 2016a,b) and in isolated triples in the field (Silsbee & Tremaine 2017). Finally, BH binaries in orbit around a supermassive BH (SMBH) in galactic nuclei (GNs) also represent hierarchical triples (Antonini & Perets 2012; VanLandingham et al. 2016; Hoang et al. 2017; Randall & Xianyu 2017). In these systems, eccentricity may be increased to a value close to unity during Kozai-Lidov oscillations while the semi-major axis is fixed, and GW emission may then quickly reduce the binary separation and lead to a merger before the orbits may fully circularize. A related channel to form eccentric mergers is through dynamical multi-body interactions in dense stellar systems, which can drive the low-eccentricity inner binary to high eccentricity (Gültekin et al. 2006; O'Leary et al. 2006; Kushnir et al. 2013; Antonini & Rasio 2016). Finally, bi-

¹ <http://www.ligo.caltech.edu/>

² <http://www.ego-gw.it/>

³ <http://gwcenter.icrr.u-tokyo.ac.jp/en/>

⁴ <http://www.gw-india.org/>

nary BHs forming in clusters through binary-single interactions may also produce non-negligible eccentricities (Samsing et al. 2014; Samsing & Ramirez-Ruiz 2017; Samsing 2017).

The expected merger rate densities in the Kozai-Lidov channel are uncertain (as all other rate estimates), but expectations are $1 - 1.5 \text{ Gpc}^{-3} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ for BH binaries forming in nuclear star clusters through multi-body interactions (Antonini & Rasio 2016) and $0.14 - 6.1 \text{ Gpc}^{-3} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ in isolated triple systems (Silsbee & Tremaine 2017). Of order $1 - 5 \text{ Gpc}^{-3} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ merger rate density is expected for BH binaries forming via the Kozai-Lidov mechanism in globular clusters (GCs) (Antonini et al. 2014, 2016; Rodriguez et al. 2016a,b) and in GNs (Antonini & Perets 2012; Hoang et al. 2017). Smaller size GNs with intermediate mass BHs (VanLandingham et al. 2016) and binary BHs forming in clusters through binary-single interaction (Samsing 2017) may produce higher rates. An attractive feature of these merger channels is that it offers a solution to the so-called “final AU problem”, i.e. on how the BHs or their progenitors shrink to a separation below which GW emission can drive the binary to merge within a Hubble time (Stone et al. 2017).

Here we focus on another channel which also naturally solves the final AU problem and leads to eccentric mergers. These are close fly-bys between single objects in dense stellar systems, which form binaries due to GW emission. If the velocity dispersion is high in the host environment as in GNs then the binary pericenter distance must be small for a binary to form in this way. This implies that the source will either form in the LIGO frequency band, and/or remain eccentric in the LIGO band until merger. Despite the required small impact parameter, the merger rate in this channel may be high due to the extremely high number density of BHs in the mass-segregated cusps of GNs.⁵ O’Leary et al. (2009) showed that the expected aLIGO detection rate at design sensitivity for eccentric mergers forming through GW capture in GNs is higher than $\sim 100 \text{ yr}^{-1}$ if the BH mass function extends to masses above $25 M_{\odot}$ (see also Kocsis & Levin 2012). Since that publication, such heavy BHs have been observed in several LIGO/VIRGO detections (Abbott et al. 2016a, 2017a,b). This also means that the aLIGO detection rate of highly eccentric binaries may be dominated by sources in GN that form through GW capture.

In this paper, we determine the region of initial orbital parameters including eccentricity, pericenter distance, and masses where eccentric binary black holes (EBBHs) may form, the probability density function (PDF) of EBBH mergers as a function of these parameters, and calculate the expected PDF of initial orbital parameters. In particular, we determine the PDF of eccentricity at the time the GW signal of EBBHs enter the aLIGO band. Additionally, we estimate how circular these binaries become when they reach the last stable orbit (LSO). We also calculate the merger rate distribution as a function of total mass and mass-ratio in a single GN in this channel. Recently, O’Leary et al. (2016) showed that in GCs, independently of the BH mass function, the likelihood of merger is proportional to M^4 , where M is the total mass of the binary and comparable component masses are most common. Furthermore, Kocsis et al. (2017) found that a different universal relation holds for the likelihood of primordial BH binaries formed in the early universe. Such universal results may be valuable to statistically disentangle different source

populations and to determine the BH mass function therein.

In a companion paper, Gondán et al. (2017), we calculate the expected parameter measurement errors of eccentric mergers, and show that the initial orbital eccentricity can be measured to sub-percent accuracy with the aLIGO-AdV-KAGRA GW detector network. Thus, the predicted merger rate distributions as functions of source parameters (particularly eccentricity) may be used to confirm or to rule out this formation mechanism.

GW signals of EBBHs are very different from that of standard quasi-circular inspirals. At early times these GW signals in time domain consist of repeated bursts where the separation between successive bursts shrinks and their amplitudes change as a function of time, and the waveform transforms into an eccentric quasi-periodic chirp signal before the merger. Eccentricity leads to multiple orbital frequency harmonics in the waveform, pericenter precession causes each harmonic to split into a frequency triplet, and eccentricity also changes the GW phase evolution. This makes them rich in features and very unique among other signals. Furthermore, these GW signals are more luminous in the aLIGO band than circular sources, which makes them detectable to larger distances (O’Leary et al. 2009).

However, Brown & Zimmerman (2010) have shown that methods based on circular binary templates could miss eccentric signals if the orbital eccentricity exceeds 0.1 at the time these GW signals enter the aLIGO band. As we will show in this paper, a significant fraction of EBBHs forming through GW capture in GN hosts have $e > 0.1$ when their GW signals reach the aLIGO band. In such cases, search methods using circular binary templates will be ineffective in finding GW signals of these EBBHs.

Power stacking and coherent search methods were developed to find the signals of stellar-mass highly-eccentric BBHs in data streams of GW detectors (Tai et al. 2014; Tiwari et al. 2016). Both methods achieve substantially better sensitivity for EBBH signals than existing localized burst searches or chirp-like template-based search methods. Moreover, a robust and computationally efficient method was also developed for detecting low to moderate-eccentricity ($0 \leq e \leq 0.6$) low-mass compact binaries (Coughlin et al. 2015). However, the complex nature of EBBH waveforms makes it necessary to develop more efficient search algorithms to detect these GW signals for moderately small signal-to-noise ratio. Such algorithms would largely benefit from the detailed prior knowledge of source parameter distributions in the parameter space, in particular the likely range of parameter values, which must be covered with the search pipeline.

Once a source is detected, different algorithms are used to recover its physical parameters. For compact binary coalescence sources on circular inspiral orbits, several algorithms have been developed for this purpose, e.g. BAYESTAR (Singer & Price 2016), LALINFERENCE (Veitch et al. 2015), GSTLAL (Cannon et al. 2012; Privitera et al. 2014), COHERENT WAVEBURST (Klimenko et al. 2016), BAYESWAVE (Cornish & Littenberg 2015), and LALINFERENCEBURST (Veitch et al. 2015). The development of algorithms recovering the parameters of compact binaries on eccentric orbits are currently underway. These algorithms will play an important role for the astrophysical interpretation of eccentric sources.

The paper is organized as follows. In Section 2, we introduce the adopted models for the GN host environment and stellar populations properties. In Section 3, we summarize the phases of GW capture induced binary evolution. In Section 4,

⁵ formation rates for these scattering events are proportional to the square of the number density

we describe Monte Carlo (MC) calculations of the parameter distribution of merger rates. In Section 4.3, we present an analytical derivation of the rates which captures the leading order behavior. In Section 5, we present our results in two parts. First, we present the distributions of orbital parameters of EBBHs at different stages of their time evolution, then we determine the merger rate distributions and the corresponding aLIGO detection rate distributions. We also identify characteristics of GN host environments to which the results are sensitive. Finally, we summarize the results of the paper and draw conclusions in Section 6. Details of analytic calculations can be found in Appendices A, B, C.

We use $G = 1 = c$ units in this paper.

2. GALACTIC NUCLEI AND RELAXED STELLAR POPULATIONS

Here we describe the characteristics of GN host environments (Section 2.1) and stellar populations (Section 2.2) that we adopt in this study.

2.1. Galactic nuclei

GNs are assumed to be relaxed systems of spherically symmetric stellar populations (e.g. white dwarfs or WDs, main sequence stars or MSs, NSs, and BHs) gravitationally bound to a central SMBH. The relaxation of multi-mass stellar populations around a SMBH has been thoroughly investigated (Bahcall & Wolf 1977; Freitag et al. 2006; Hopman & Alexander 2006; Alexander & Hopman 2009; Keshet et al. 2009; O’Leary et al. 2009), and found that within the radius of influence of the GN objects segregate to the central regions and form a power-law number density profile, $n(r) \propto r^{-\alpha}$ in which the α exponent is higher for more massive objects. The radius of influence is given as

$$r_{\max} = GM_{\text{SMBH}}/\sigma_*^2, \quad (1)$$

where M_{SMBH} is the mass of the SMBH, σ_* is the velocity dispersion of the underlying stellar populations in the nucleus near the SMBH, and we use the $M_{\text{SMBH}}-\sigma_*$ relationship (Tremaine et al. 2002; Walcher et al. 2005; Misgeld & Hilker 2011; Norris et al. 2014):

$$M_{\text{SMBH}} \simeq 1.3 \times 10^8 M_{\odot} \left(\frac{\sigma_*}{200 \text{ km s}^{-1}} \right)^4. \quad (2)$$

We choose the lower limit of the SMBH mass range to be $10^5 M_{\odot}$ (Barth et al. 2005; Greene & Ho 2006). We conservatively set the upper limit of the SMBH mass to $10^7 M_{\odot}$ corresponding to relaxed stellar populations (see Appendix A.1 for details).

For spherically symmetric and relaxed GNs, we use the Bahcall & Wolf (1976) one-body phase space distribution $f(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{v})$ generalized for a multi-mass system (O’Leary et al. 2009) to derive the distribution of the magnitude of relative velocity between single objects (see Appendices B.1 and B.2). For objects with mass m , this has the form

$$f_m(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{v}) = C_m E(r, v)^{p_m} \quad (3)$$

if $r_{\min} \leq r \leq r_{\max}$ and $E(r, v) > 0$, C_m is a normalization constant,

$$E(r, v) = \frac{M_{\text{SMBH}}}{r} - \frac{v^2}{2} \quad (4)$$

is the Keplerian binding energy in the field of the SMBH, and the p_m exponent depends on mass due to mass segregation.

For the light stellar components, such as MSs, WDs, and NSs, $p_m \approx 0$, and for the heavier components such as BHs,

$$p_m = p_0 \frac{m}{m_{\text{BH,max}}}, \quad (5)$$

where $m_{\text{BH,max}}$ is the highest possible BH mass in the population and $p_0 \approx 0.5-0.6$ based on Fokker-Planck simulations (O’Leary et al. 2009). We consider the standard value of p_0 to be 0.5. Equation (4) is valid outside the loss cone (Shapiro & Lightman 1976; Syer & Ulmer 1999). We assume it to be valid between $r_{\min} \leq r \leq r_{\max}$ if v is less than the escape velocity at radius r , where r_{\min} is an inner radius where the density cusp exhibits a cutoff. We calculate r_{\min} by requiring that (i) the number density profile of these populations reaches steady-state and forms a power-law density cusp within the age of the galaxy; and (ii) the inspiral timescale into the SMBH is larger than the relaxation time, see Appendix A for details.

Since the binding energy is positive for objects bound to the SMBH, $E(r, v) > 0$, the velocity at distance r from the SMBH must be less than the escape velocity

$$v_{\max}(r) = \sqrt{\frac{2GM_{\text{SMBH}}}{r}}. \quad (6)$$

The 3D number density distribution of mass m objects at radius r may be obtained from Equation (3) as

$$n_m(r) = \int f_m(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{v}) d^3v = n_{\text{inf},m} \left(\frac{r}{r_{\max}} \right)^{-\alpha_m}, \quad (7)$$

where

$$\alpha_m = \frac{3}{2} + p_m, \quad (8)$$

and n_{inf} is the number density of objects at the radius of influence. For MSs of $m = 1 M_{\odot}$ this follows from the $M-\sigma$ relation Equation (2), assuming that the enclosed stellar mass within the radius of influence r_{\max} is $2M_{\text{SMBH}}$ (e.g. O’Leary et al. 2009)

$$n_{\text{inf,MS}} \equiv n_{\text{MS}}(r_{\max}) \simeq 1.38 \times 10^5 \text{ pc}^{-3} \sqrt{\frac{10^6 M_{\odot}}{M_{\text{SMBH}}}}. \quad (9)$$

We define the normalization constants n_{inf} and the exponent of the number density distribution α_m separately for the different stellar species next in Section 2.2.

2.2. Stellar populations in galactic nuclei

The initial mass-functions (IMF), which extends from the brown dwarf boundary $\sim 0.1 M_{\odot}$ to $\sim 100 M_{\odot}$ (e.g. the Salpeter 1955 IMF and its subsequent refinements, the Miller & Scalo 1979 and Kroupa 2001 IMFs) result in evolved populations that naturally separate into two mass scales, the $\sim 1 M_{\odot}$ scale of low-mass MSs, WDs, and NSs, and the $\sim 10 M_{\odot}$ scale of stellar-mass BHs, Wolf Rayet, O-, and B-stars. In case of a GN, the shape of the present-day mass function (PMF) varies significantly above the scale of $\sim 10 M_{\odot}$ (Alexander & Hopman 2009). The typical PMF in GNs is not well understood due to the fact that star formation deep in the potential well of a SMBH can be very different from that of the field. Bartko et al. (2010) find evidence that the stellar disks in the GN of the Galaxy is extremely top-heavy. Lu et al. (2013) infer that the mass function of these young stars is proportional to $m^{-1.7 \pm 0.2}$, which implies that the number of massive stars is currently higher than that for a standard Salpeter mass function.

We follow [Alexander & Hopman \(2009\)](#) and assume single-mass MS, WD and NS populations in GNs with component masses $1M_{\odot}$, $0.6M_{\odot}$, and $1.4M_{\odot}$, respectively. The results are not sensitive to this assumption, see Appendix A.

We normalize the number density distribution for WD, MS, and NS populations in Equations (7) as

$$n_{\text{inf},i} = n_{\text{inf,MS}} C_i, \quad (10)$$

where i labels $\{\text{WD, MS, NS}\}$, and set the number density exponents to

$$\alpha_{\text{MS}} = \alpha_{\text{WD}} = 1.4 \quad \text{and} \quad \alpha_{\text{NS}} = 1.5 \quad (11)$$

([Hopman & Alexander 2006](#)). C_i represents number fraction ratios of MSs, WDs, and NSs as $1 : 0.1 : 0.01$ for continuous star-forming populations ([Alexander 2005](#)), implying that

$$C_{\text{MS}} = 1, \quad C_{\text{WD}} = 0.1, \quad C_{\text{NS}} = 0.01 \frac{3 - \alpha_{\text{NS}}}{3 - \alpha_{\text{MS}}}. \quad (12)$$

We carry out calculations for two types of BH PMF models: a simple single-component and a power-law multi-mass distribution as follows.

1. In the single-mass BH population model we assume that all BHs have $m_{\text{BH}} = 10M_{\odot}$ following [Morris \(1993\)](#), [Miralda-Escudé & Gould \(2000\)](#), and [Alexander & Hopman \(2009\)](#) for 10 Gyr old coeval population, implying that the number density exponent in equation (9) is $\alpha_{\text{BH,s}} = 2$ and to determine $C_{\text{BH,s}}$ we account for BHs segregated into the nucleus. For the Milky Way, as many as $\sim 20,000$ BHs with $10M_{\odot}$ each are expected to have segregated into the nucleus ([Morris 1993](#); [Miralda-Escudé & Gould 2000](#); [Hopman & Alexander 2006](#); [Freitag et al. 2006](#)). Since the number of BHs segregated into the GN is proportional to the mass of the SMBH through the infall rate of BHs (see Equation (9) in [Miralda-Escudé & Gould \(2000\)](#)), therefore it can be approximated as

$$N_{\text{BH}} \approx 20,000 \times \frac{M_{\text{SMBH}}}{M_{\text{SgrA}^*}}. \quad (13)$$

Here $M_{\text{SgrA}^*} = 4.3 \times 10^6 M_{\odot}$ is the mass of the SMBH, Sgr A* in the Milky Way-size nucleus ([Gillessen et al. 2009](#))⁶. The number density distribution of BHs in this single-mass model is of the form

$$n_{\text{BH,s}} = C_{\text{BH,s}} n_{\text{inf,MS}} \left(\frac{r}{r_{\text{max}}} \right)^{-\alpha_{\text{BH,s}}}, \quad (14)$$

where $C_{\text{BH,s}}$ can be determined using Equation (10) together with Equation (13), which gives

$$C_{\text{BH,s}} = 0.023 \frac{3 - \alpha_{\text{BH,s}}}{3 - \alpha_{\text{MS}}}. \quad (15)$$

2. In the multi-mass BH population model we assume a power-law PMF $m^{-\beta}$ following [Alexander & Hopman \(2009\)](#) for 10 Gyr of continuous star formation. The probability distribution function of BH mass is then

$$\mathcal{F}(m_{\text{BH}}) = \frac{(1 - \beta) m_{\text{BH}}^{-\beta}}{m_{\text{BH,max}}^{1-\beta} - m_{\text{BH,min}}^{1-\beta}}. \quad (16)$$

We consider β in the range $[1, 3]$, and choose its standard value arbitrarily to be $\beta \equiv 2.35$ although the exponent for BHs need not be related to the Salpeter IMF of

massive stars ([Salpeter 1955](#)). This range is consistent with the currently announced GW detections ([Abbott et al. 2017a](#)). We set $m_{\text{BH,min}} = 5M_{\odot}$ based on the observations of X-ray binaries ([Bailyn et al. 1998](#); [Özel et al. 2010](#); [Farr et al. 2011](#); [Belczynski et al. 2012](#)) and we set the fiducial value for the highest possible BH mass to be $m_{\text{BH,max}} = 30M_{\odot}$ but also explore cases between $10M_{\odot}$ and $80M_{\odot}$ ([Belczynski et al. 2010](#)). Taking into account the mass distribution of BHs, the number density normalization at the radius of influence in Equation (7) for BHs in a multi-mass BH population is

$$n_{\text{BH,m}}(m_{\text{BH}}) = n_{\text{MS}} \mathcal{F}(m_{\text{BH}}) C_{\text{BH,m}}, \quad (17)$$

where $C_{\text{BH,m}}$ is set numerically by the total number of BHs inside the GN as

$$N_{\text{BH}} = \int_{m_{\text{BH,min}}}^{m_{\text{BH,max}}} dm_{\text{BH}} n_{\text{BH,m}}(m_{\text{BH}}) \times \int_0^{r_{\text{max}}} 4\pi r^2 \left(\frac{r}{r_{\text{max}}} \right)^{-\alpha_{\text{BH,m}}} dr. \quad (18)$$

Here $\alpha_{\text{BH,m}}$ is given by combining Equations (5) and (8).

3. PHASES OF BINARY EVOLUTION

In this section, we introduce the GW capture binary formation mechanism and calculate resulting distribution of initial orbital parameters. Then we examine the evolution through the eccentric inspiral and the long term interaction between the formed binary and a third object in simulations.

In the following, we denote the masses of BHs forming the binary by m_A and m_B , the symmetric mass ratio of the binary by $\eta = (m_A m_B) / (m_A + m_B)^2$, and the total mass by $M_{\text{tot}} = m_A + m_B$, and the mass ratio by $q = m_A / m_B$. The reduced mass and symmetric mass ratio satisfy $\mu = \eta M_{\text{tot}}$ and $\eta = q / (q + 1)^2$. Similar to [O'Leary et al. \(2009\)](#), we define the dimensionless pericenter distance as $\rho_p = r_p / M_{\text{tot}}$, where r_p is the pericenter distance changing with each orbit.

3.1. Formation of binaries through GW capture and the eccentric inspiral

Two BHs form a binary if they undergo a close encounter, and they emit enough energy in form of GWs to become bound. Due to the relativistic nature of such events and the low velocity dispersion compared to $c = 1$ in GN hosts, the encounters are almost always nearly parabolic ([Quinlan & Shapiro 1987](#); [Lee & Bradley 1993](#)). Thus, the initial orbit of the formed binary is typically highly eccentric with $e \sim 1$. In this limit, the amount of energy emitted in GWs during the encounter is

$$\delta E_{\text{GW}} = - \frac{85\pi\eta^2 M_{\text{tot}}^{9/2}}{12\sqrt{2}r_{p0}^{7/2}} \quad (19)$$

([Peters & Mathews 1963](#); [Turner 1977](#)), where r_{p0} is the distance of closest approach (we use 0 in the lower index to denote initial values of parameters throughout the paper, i.e. their values at the time of EBBH formation):

$$r_{p0} = \left(\sqrt{\frac{1}{b^2} + \frac{M_{\text{tot}}^2}{b^4 w^4} + \frac{M_{\text{tot}}}{b^2 w^2}} \right)^{-1} \quad (20)$$

⁶ We choose $M_{\text{SMBH}} = M_{\text{SgrA}^*}$ in our fiducial numerical calculations, but also explore other values.

(O’Leary et al. 2009), where b is the impact parameter of the encounter, and w is the magnitude of relative velocity between the BHs forming the EBBH.

The initial properties of the EBBH are determined by the encountering system’s final energy E_{fin} , and final angular momentum L_{fin} , after the first encounter, where

$$E_{\text{fin}} = E_{\text{kin}} + \delta E_{\text{GW}}, \quad (21)$$

$$L_{\text{fin}} = M_{\text{tot}} b \eta w + \delta L, \quad (22)$$

where $E_{\text{kin}} = \mu w^2/2$ is the kinetic energy in the center of mass system, and δL is the amount of angular momentum lost during an encounter (Peters 1964). O’Leary et al. (2009) found that δL is negligible for nearly all first encounters, therefore we set $\delta L \approx 0$. If the final energy of the system after the encounter is negative, $E_{\text{fin}} < 0$, then the system remains bound with an initial semi-major axis of

$$a_0 = \frac{\eta M_{\text{tot}}^2}{2|E_{\text{fin}}|}, \quad (23)$$

and with an initial eccentricity of

$$e_0 = \sqrt{1 - \frac{2|E_{\text{fin}}|w^2b^2}{M_{\text{tot}}^3\eta}}. \quad (24)$$

Note that the initial pericenter distance of the EBBH system r_{p0} can be expressed in terms of e_0 and a_0 as

$$r_{p0} = a_0(1 - e_0). \quad (25)$$

The criterion $E_{\text{fin}} < 0$ for the two BHs to form a bound binary sets an upper limit on the impact parameter of the approach (O’Leary et al. 2009). Additionally, a lower limit on b is set by the fact that we require the BHs to avoid direct coalescence during the first close approach. Therefore, to leading order, a bound EBBH system can form if b satisfies

$$b_{\text{min}} \equiv \frac{4M_{\text{tot}}}{w} < b < \left(\frac{340\pi\eta}{3}\right)^{1/7} \frac{M_{\text{tot}}}{w^{9/7}} \equiv b_{\text{max}}. \quad (26)$$

Here the upper limit corresponds to Equations (19) and (21), and the lower limit is valid in the test-particle limit around a Schwarzschild BH (e.g Kocsis et al. 2006; O’Leary et al. 2009). The leading order approximation in the allowed range of b values expressed by Equation (26) is in a good match with 2.5 and 3.5 order post-Newtonian (PN) simulations for relative velocity $w \lesssim 0.01$ (see Figure 1. in Kocsis & Levin 2012)). Relativistic corrections modify the capture cross section by less than 10% (Kocsis & Levin 2012)

Due to the escape velocity v_{max} at radius r from the SMBH (Equation 6), the initial relative velocity is bounded by

$$0 \leq w \leq 2v_{\text{max}}(r) = \sqrt{8M_{\text{SMBH}}/r}. \quad (27)$$

The allowed range of initial binary parameters ρ_{p0} and e_0 may be calculated from the bounds on b and w given by Equations (26) and (27) using Equations (23) and (25).

After the binary is formed with initial parameters e_0 and ρ_{p0} , it evolves due to GW radiation reaction. We use the leading order orbital evolution equation (Peters 1964)

$$\rho_{\text{p}}(e) = \frac{c_0}{M_{\text{tot}}} \frac{e^{12/19}}{(1+e)} \left(1 + \frac{121}{304} e^2\right)^{\frac{870}{2299}}, \quad (28)$$

where c_0/M_{tot} may be expressed with e_0 and ρ_{p0} , by solving Equation (28) for $\rho_{\text{p}} = \rho_{p0}$ and $e = e_0$.

The evolution equation (28) is valid when the two BHs are relatively far from each other’s horizon, for $\rho_{\text{p}} \gg 2$, up until the binary reaches its last stable orbit (LSO). After that the evolution is no longer quasi periodic and the BHs quickly coalesce. In the leading order approximation for infinite mass ratio and zero spins, the eccentricity of the LSO, e_{LSO} , can be calculated by numerically solving the following equation (Cutler et al. 1994)

$$\rho_{\text{p}}(e_{\text{LSO}}) = \frac{6 + 2e_{\text{LSO}}}{1 + e_{\text{LSO}}}. \quad (29)$$

for e_{LSO} using Equation (28). The initial pericenter distance is set uniquely by e_{LSO} and e_0 according to

$$\rho_{p0} = \frac{6 + 2e_{\text{LSO}}}{1 + e_0} \frac{e_0^{12/19}}{e_{\text{LSO}}^{12/19}} \left[\frac{1 + (121/304)e_0^2}{1 + (121/304)e_{\text{LSO}}^2} \right]^{\frac{870}{2299}}. \quad (30)$$

In the limit $e_0 \approx 1$, which we find to be the relevant case,

$$\rho_{p0} \approx \frac{3 + e_{\text{LSO}}}{e_{\text{LSO}}^{12/19}} \left(1 + \frac{121}{304} e_{\text{LSO}}^2\right)^{-\frac{870}{2299}}. \quad (31)$$

We invert Equation (31) numerically to obtain $e_{\text{LSO}}(\rho_{p0})$. The result is well fitted⁷ by

$$e_{\text{LSO}} = 6.3096 \rho_{p0}^{-1.599}. \quad (32)$$

This shows that generally ρ_{p0} is a monotonically decreasing function of e_{LSO} , where $\rho_{p0} \gtrsim 10$ corresponds to $e_{\text{LSO}} \lesssim 0.19$.

3.2. Interaction with a third object

Although the stellar number density is the highest in GNs, O’Leary et al. (2009) have shown that the binaries which form by GW capture are so tight that they typically merge before encountering a third object that would alter their orbital parameters, we conservatively neglect the rare EBBHs in our Monte Carlo (MC) sample that have an encounter with a third object before the merger of the EBBH (Section 4.2), i.e. if the encounter timescale is shorter than the merger timescale,

$$t_{\text{merge}} > t_{\text{enc}}. \quad (33)$$

The typical timescale for a close encounter between a binary and a single object can be approximated as

$$t_{\text{enc}} \approx \frac{w^3}{12\pi M_{\text{tot}}^2 n_{\text{tot}}} \quad (34)$$

(O’Leary et al. 2009), where

$$n_{\text{tot}} = n_{\text{WD}}(r) + n_{\text{MS}}(r) + n_{\text{NS}}(r) + n_{\text{BH}}(r) \quad (35)$$

is the combined number density of all objects at distance r . By substituting Equation (28) into Equation (5.7) in Peters (1964), the time remaining until coalescence is

$$t_{\text{merge}}(\rho_{p0}, m_A, m_B, e_0) = \frac{15 c_0^4(e_0, \rho_{p0})}{304 M_{\text{tot}}^3 \eta} \mathcal{F}(e_{\text{LSO}}, e_0), \quad (36)$$

where

$$\mathcal{F}(A, B) \equiv \int_A^B de \frac{e^{29/19} \left(1 + \frac{121}{304} e^2\right)^{\frac{1181}{2299}}}{(1 - e^2)^{3/2}}. \quad (37)$$

⁷ We use the method of least squares to fit the prefactor and exponent. The fit error is 0.001 for both parameters for the 95% confidence bounds in the range $\rho_{p0} \in [8, 1000]$. Most EBBHs form in this range in GNs (see Section 5.2).

Note, that $\mathcal{F}(e_{\text{LSO}}, e_0) \approx \mathcal{F}(0, e_0)$ within 0.1% for $e_{\text{LSO}} \ll e_0 \sim 1$ and thus t_{merge} can practically be approximated as

$$t_{\text{merge}}(\rho_{p0}, m_A, m_B, e_0) \approx \frac{15 c_0^4(e_0, \rho_{p0})}{304 M_{\text{tot}}^3 \eta} \mathcal{F}(0, e_0). \quad (38)$$

Since the fraction of binaries that satisfy Equation (33) represents a small fraction of all objects (Section 5.2), neglecting this population does not bias the initial binary orbital parameter distributions.

4. DISTRIBUTIONS OF INITIAL ORBITAL PARAMETERS AND EBBH MERGERS

In this section, we derive the distributions of the masses and the initial orbital parameters of EBBHs in GNs.

We parameterize the formation of an EBBH through GW capture by four parameters: the two masses of the BHs involved (m_A and m_B), the magnitude of the relative velocity between the two BHs (w), and the impact parameter of the approach (b). Here we first treat m_A and m_B as being fixed, while w and b as free parameters. We use the phase space distribution function $f_A(\mathbf{r}_A, \mathbf{v}_A)$ and $f_B(\mathbf{r}_B, \mathbf{v}_B)$, given by Equation (3). The distributions depend on the masses m_A and m_B through the exponents p_A and p_B in Equations (3) and (5) as heavier components form steeper density cusps due to mass segregation.

The differential rate of EBBH mergers involving BHs A and B can be given in the 12-dimensional phase space of these two objects as

$$d^{12}\Gamma_{AB} = \sigma w f_A(\mathbf{r}_A, \mathbf{v}_A) f_B(\mathbf{r}_B, \mathbf{v}_B) \times d^3 r_A d^3 r_B d^3 v_A d^3 v_B, \quad (39)$$

where $\sigma \equiv \sigma(w) = \pi b_{\text{max}}^2(w) - \pi b_{\text{min}}^2(w)$ is the cross section for two BHs to form an EBBH during their encounter, see Equation (26) for b_{min} and b_{max} .

4.1. Analytical estimates

The total merger rates may be obtained from integrating Eq. (39) over phase space. The partial merger rate distribution as a function of parameters (e.g. radius in the GN, mass, initial eccentricity, and pericenter distance) may be obtained by integrating only over the complementary phase space dimensions. We refer the reader to Appendix B for details and present the results of the calculations in Section 5.

4.2. The Monte Carlo code

To generate a random sample of EBBHs with component masses m_A and m_B , we first generate $\sim 10^3$ random radius values from the galactic center over the radius range $r \in [r_{\text{min}}^{A,B}, r_{\text{max}}]$ using Equations (55) and (56). We then randomly draw a pair of w and b for each r from $P_{AB}(w, b)$ using Equations (B30)–(B31) in Appendix B.

EBBHs can form with w as high as $w \simeq 0.05$ near $r_{\text{min}}^{A,B}$. The region of validity of equation (26) for $b_{\text{min}} \propto w^{-1}$ and $b_{\text{max}} \propto w^{-9/7}$ is as follows. For high w , the condition $b_{\text{max}}(w) > b_{\text{min}}(w)$ may be violated over

$$w_{\text{max},b} = \frac{1}{4^3} \sqrt{\frac{85\pi\eta}{3}}. \quad (40)$$

These systems cannot form an eccentric binary system, but may only suffer a direct head-on collision. We discard all such (w, b) pairs in our MC sample that do not satisfy $w \leq w_{\text{max},b}$.

Figure 1. A Monte Carlo realization of the EBBH parameters in the space of initial eccentricity and initial dimensionless pericenter distance $\rho_{p0} = r/M_{\text{tot}}$ showing the allowed parameter values of EBBHs. The initial eccentricity is typically very close to unity, so we show $\log(1 - e_0^2)$ to resolve the deviation from $e_0 = 1$. The allowed region is bounded by curves that represent physical constraints on the binary formation and evolution as indicated and explained in the text. We assume a Milky Way-size nucleus with $M_{\text{SgrA}^*} = 4.3 \times 10^6 M_{\odot}$ and show mergers with $m_A = m_B = 10 M_{\odot}$ within a BH population with $dN/dm \propto m^{-2.35}$, a maximum BH mass of $m_{\text{BH,max}} = 30 M_{\odot}$, and a mass segregation parameter $p_0 = 0.5$ (Equation 5). We find that 99% of EBBHs (represented here by green dots) merge before a dynamical encounter may happen with a third object (i.e. $t_{\text{enc}} > t_{\text{merge}}$ holds), shown by a solid red line.

We find numerically that only $\lesssim 0.01\%$ ($\lesssim 1\%$) of EBBHs form with $w \gtrsim 0.05$ ($w \gtrsim w_{\text{max},b}$) over the considered ranges of BH mass, SMBH mass, and BH population parameters, thus direct head on collisions represent a negligible fraction of sources.

Furthermore, we keep only those (w, b) pairs that avoid interaction with a third object satisfying Equation (33).

For each random sample of (w, b) we calculate the corresponding initial pericenter distance and eccentricity of the binary (ρ_{p0}, e_0) using formulae introduced in Section 3.1.

Given that most of these binaries have $e_0 \sim 1$, we introduce the new variable

$$\epsilon_0 \equiv 1 - e_0^2 \quad (41)$$

in order to represent the PDF of e_0 accurately in the vicinity of unity (see Section 5).

4.3. Bounds on the initial orbital parameters

Figure 1 shows a 2.5×10^5 MC sample of EBBHs in the $\epsilon_0 - \rho_{p0}$ plane for a SMBH mass of $4.3 \times 10^6 M_{\odot}$ for EBBHs having $m_A = m_B = 30 M_{\odot}$. The distribution is bounded by 5 curves, where one of the conditions of a stable EBBH formation is violated as labeled. We discuss these conditions next and derive analytic approximations for each of them.

Stable EBBH formation from two single objects bound to the central SMBH requires:

- (I) avoid direct collision without forming a stable EBBH, $b > b_{\text{min}}$;
- (II) avoid escape to infinity $b < b_{\text{max}}$
- (III) The initial kinetic energy must be positive $E_{\text{kin}} \geq 0$. The two BHs radiate more GW energy during their encounter than the total initial kinetic energy, $\delta E_{\text{GW}} < E_{\text{kin}}$, which implies that $E_{\text{fin}} \geq \delta E_{\text{GW}}$;

- (IV) EBBHs should not interact with a third object throughout their evolutions, $t_{\text{merge}} < t_{\text{enc}}$;
- (V) BHs bound to the central SMBH have an initial velocity less than the escape velocity $v_{\text{max}}(r)$, which sets a bound on the maximum relative speed, $w < w_{\text{max}}(r) \equiv 2v_{\text{max}}(r)$ (Equation 27). Objects exist in the GN within the radius of influence of the SMBH sufficiently far to avoid infall into the SMBH due to GW emission, $r_{\text{min}}^{A,B} \leq r \leq r_{\text{max}}$. This sets a bound on w .

The above five criteria define sharp boundaries in the $\epsilon_0 - \rho_{p0}$ plane as follows:

- (I) From Equation (20), the leading order approximation for $\rho_{p0} = r_{p0}/M_{\text{tot}}$ in terms of w is

$$\rho_{p0} \simeq \frac{b^2 w^2}{2M_{\text{tot}}^2}. \quad (42)$$

Using Equation (42) and the definition of b_{min} given in Equation (26), the criterion $b > b_{\text{min}}$ can be translated into the constraint $\rho_{p0} > 8$ to leading post-Newtonian order.

- (II) The criterion $b < b_{\text{max}}$ means that the two encountering BHs must pass each other close enough to become bound follow GW emission, and thus E_{fin} must satisfy $E_{\text{fin}} < 0$. Using Equation (21) and the definition of ϵ_0 given in (41), this can be translated into a constraint $e_0 < 1$ or equivalently $\epsilon_0 > 0$. Moreover, this criterion must be satisfied for the possible range of w values in the GN, $0 \leq w < w_{\text{max}}$. Here w_{max} is the highest w occurring in the GN below $w_{\text{max},b}$. Combining Equations (21) and (46) together with Equation (19), w may be expressed in Equation (34) in terms of ϵ_0 and ρ_{p0} as

$$w \simeq \left(\frac{85\pi\eta}{6\sqrt{2}\rho_{p0}^{7/2}} - \frac{\epsilon_0}{2\rho_{p0}} \right)^{1/2}. \quad (43)$$

Combining Equation (42) with Equation (43), b can be expressed in terms of ρ_{p0} and ϵ_0 as

$$b = \sqrt{2\rho_{p0}} M_{\text{tot}} \left(\frac{85\pi\eta}{6\sqrt{2}\rho_{p0}^{7/2}} - \frac{\epsilon_0}{2\rho_{p0}} \right)^{1/4}. \quad (44)$$

Conversely, solving for ρ_{p0} and ϵ_0 , gives Equation (42) and

$$\epsilon_0(b, w) = \frac{340\pi\eta M_{\text{tot}}^5}{3b^5 w^5} - \frac{b^2 w^4}{M_{\text{tot}}^2}. \quad (45)$$

The constraint on b in Equation (26) gives a boundary curve in the $\epsilon_0 - \rho_{p0}$ plane.

- (III) Using Equations (21) and (42), E_{fin} can be expressed in terms of ϵ_0 and ρ_{p0} as

$$E_{\text{fin}} \simeq -\frac{M_{\text{tot}}\eta\epsilon_0}{4\rho_{p0}}. \quad (46)$$

Finally, using Equation (19) together with Equation (46), the criterion $\delta E_{\text{GW}} < E_{\text{fin}}$ defines the following upper limit on ϵ_0 :

$$\epsilon_0 < \frac{85\pi\eta}{3\sqrt{2}} \rho_{p0}^{-5/2}. \quad (47)$$

Note that the $\delta E_{\text{GW}} = E_{\text{fin}}$ case corresponds to the $w = 0$ limit (see Equation (21)).

- (IV) The boundary curve in the $\epsilon_0 - \rho_{p0}$ plane defined by $t_{\text{merge}} = t_{\text{enc}}$ can only be constructed numerically by expressing all terms in equations (34) and (36) as functions of ϵ_0 and ρ_{p0} . a_0 and c_0 can be expressed in terms of ϵ_0 and ρ_{p0} using Equations (25) and (28). This boundary must be calculated at each radius in the GN because n_{tot} depends on r (Equation 35). However, an upper boundary can be constructed for the whole EBBH population merging in the GN by choosing $r = r_{\text{max}}$, which we use to identify that region of the $\epsilon_0 - \rho_{p0}$ plane in which EBBHs surely interact with a third object before the merger phase of the EBBH evolution.
- (V) BHs A and B should have a relative speed, w , lower than $2v_{\text{max}}(r)$ at distance r from the center of the nucleus, i.e. $w < w_{\text{max}}(r) \equiv 2v_{\text{max}}(r) < w_{\text{max}}$. Using Equation (43), the criterion $w < w_{\text{max}}$ can be expressed as

$$\epsilon_0 > \frac{85\pi\eta}{3\sqrt{2}} \rho_{p0}^{-5/2} - 2\rho_{p0} w_{\text{max}}^2(r_{\text{min}}^{A,B}) \quad (48)$$

in the $\epsilon_0 - \rho_{p0}$ plane.

These bounds on ϵ_0 and ρ_{p0} lead to the following scaling relations. The expressions of b_{min} and b_{max} defined by Equation (26) may be expressed in the form $M_{\text{tot}} w^h \eta^\alpha$ where $h = -9/7$ and -1 and $\alpha = 0$ and $1/7$, respectively. Thus the impact parameter lies in the range

$$b \propto M_{\text{tot}} w^h \eta^\alpha, \quad -9/7 \leq h \leq -1, \quad 0 \leq \alpha \leq 1/7. \quad (49)$$

These relations together with Equation (42) describing ρ_{p0} may be written as

$$\rho_{p0} \propto w^\beta \eta^{2\alpha}, \quad -4/7 \leq \beta \leq 0. \quad (50)$$

To get a similar expression for ϵ_0 , we first examine E_{fin} . Combining Equations (19) and (21) together with Equations (49) and (50), E_{fin} can be given as

$$E_{\text{fin}} = C_1 \eta M_{\text{tot}} w^2 - C_2 M_{\text{tot}} w^{-7(h+1)} \eta^{2-7\alpha}, \quad (51)$$

where C_1 and C_2 are constants. Since $w \ll 1$ for encounters over the considered ranges of BH mass, SMBH mass, and BH population parameters (Section 4.2), therefore E_{fin} is dominated by its second term, and thereby scales as

$$E_{\text{fin}} \propto -M_{\text{tot}} w^{-7(h+1)} \eta^{2-7\alpha}. \quad (52)$$

Finally, using Equations (21) and (49) together with Equation (52), yields

$$\epsilon_0 \propto w^\gamma \eta^\kappa, \quad 0 \leq \gamma \leq 10/7, \quad 2/7 \leq \kappa \leq 1. \quad (53)$$

These relations help interpret the results for MC simulations given next.

5. RESULTS

We now present the PDF of initial binary parameters describing EBBH events.

5.1. Radial distribution of EBBH mergers in galactic nuclei

Let us now determine the relative encounter rate as a function of the radius from the center of the GN, $P_{AB}(r)$, for objects with masses m_A and m_B .

Figure 2. Probability density $\log_{10}(P_{AB}(\log_{10}(r)))$ of an EBBH formed by BHs with masses m_A and m_B merging at r from the central SMBH of a Milky Way-size nucleus. In this example, the mass of the central SMBH is $M_{\text{SgrA}^*} = 4.3 \times 10^6 M_{\odot}$, and stellar populations surrounding the SMBH are assumed to form spherically symmetric and relaxed populations within the radius of influence of the SMBH, r_{max} . We give $P_{AB}(r)$ using Equations (55) and (56), for various combinations of m_A and m_B values indicated in the figure legend, and for $r \in [r_{\text{min}}^{A,B}, r_{\text{max}}]$ defined by Equations (A8) and (1). Here $r_{\text{min}}^{A,B}$ defines the inner radius at which BHs A and B can still form an EBBH (see Appendix A). Solid lines correspond to a fiducial multi-mass BH population with $dN/dm \propto m^{-2.35}$, $m_{\text{BH,max}} = 30 M_{\odot}$, and $p_0 = 0.5$ in Equation (5). The dash-dotted line corresponds to a single-mass BH population of $10 M_{\odot}$.

In Appendix B we show that the distribution of merger rates as a function of radius from the center of the GN has the form

$$\frac{\partial^3 \Gamma}{\partial r \partial m_A \partial m_B} = 4\pi^2 r^2 n_{m_A}(r) n_{m_B}(r) N_{\text{BH}}^2 \mathcal{F}(m_A) \mathcal{F}(m_B) \times C_{rA} C_{rB} (\zeta'_{\text{capt}}(r) - \zeta'_{\text{coll}}(r)), \quad (54)$$

where $n_m(r)$ and N_{BH} are given by Equations (7) and (13), respectively, C_{rA} and C_{rB} are constants defined by Equation (B8), and $\zeta'_{\text{capt}}(r)$ and $\zeta'_{\text{coll}}(r)$ are terms which follow from the cross section for GW capture and direct collisions, πb_{max}^2 and πb_{min}^2 , respectively, defined by Equations (B19) and (B20) in Appendix B.

For a multi-mass BH population, the probability distribution of the EBBH events among events with fixed BH masses m_A and m_B as a function of r may be obtained by normalizing Equation (54) over the radius range $[r_{\text{min}}^{A,B}, r_{\text{max}}]$ where BHs exist in the GN (see Appendix A). We get

$$P_{AB}(r) = C_1 \left[\left(\frac{340\pi\eta}{3} \right)^{\frac{2}{7}} r^{-\frac{3}{14} - p_0} \frac{m_A^{m_B}}{m_{\text{BH,max}}^{m_A+m_B}} - 16 r^{-\frac{1}{2} - p_0} \frac{m_A^{m_B}}{M_{\text{SMBH}}^{m_A+m_B}} \right], \quad (55)$$

where $\eta = q/(1+q)^2$, $q = m_A/m_B$, and C_1 is a normalization constant set by the requirement $\int_{r_{\text{min}}^{A,B}}^{r_{\text{max}}} P_{AB}(r) dr = 1$. For a single-mass distribution, $p_0 = 0.5$, and $m_A = m_B = \max(m_{\text{BH}}) = 10 M_{\odot}$ (i.e. $q = 1$, $\eta = 1/4$) we get

$$P_{AB}(r) = C_1 \left[\left(\frac{85\pi}{3} \right)^{\frac{2}{7}} \frac{r^{-\frac{17}{14}}}{M_{\text{SMBH}}^{11/14}} - \frac{16 r^{-3/2}}{M_{\text{SMBH}}^{1/2}} \right]. \quad (56)$$

The distribution $P_{AB}(\log_{10}(r))$ is displayed in Figure 2 for various component masses. For a single-mass BH population the profile is identical to that of the most massive BHs in a multi-mass BH population when $p_0 = 0.5$ (see Eq. 5). We find

that $P_{AB}(r)$ is steeper for more massive EBBHs as a function of radius, which is due to the steeper density gradient for higher masses (Equation 55). The profile of $P_{AB}(r)$ is weakly sensitive to mass ratio for fixed M_{tot} , i.e. proportional to $\eta^{2/7}$, due to the fact that $P_{AB}(r)$ is dominated by its first term in Equation (55). Note that the merger rate distribution on a logarithmic radial scale is $d\Gamma_{AB}/d\ln r = r d\Gamma_{AB}/dr \propto r P_{AB}(r)$. By using Equation (56) for $P_{AB}(r)$ we find that $P_{AB}(\ln r) \propto r^{-3/14}$ for the most massive BHs in the BH population, showing that the merger rate is approximately uniform on a logarithmic scale between 10^{-4} and 3 pc. In fact, roughly 50% of the most massive EBBHs are formed in the innermost 4×10^{-3} pc and 97% of the events are within 1.2 pc. However, the least massive EBBHs with $m_A = m_B = 5 M_{\odot}$, $p_0 = 0.5$, and $m_{A,B} \ll m_{\text{BH,max}}$ are distributed as $P(\ln r) \propto r^{11/14}$. Thus, only $\sim 2\%$ of them are within 4×10^{-3} pc, and only roughly 50% of them are within 1.2 pc. These low-mass binaries form preferentially further out, near the radius of influence.

5.2. Distributions of initial orbital parameters

In Appendix B we determine the EBBH merger rate distribution as a function of relative velocity and impact parameter. The initial orbital parameters e_0 and ρ_{p0} may be calculated from these parameters using Equations (20) and (21).

Figure 3 shows the merger rate distribution as a function of the initial eccentricity and dimensionless pericenter distance. Two-dimensional histograms⁸ are shown in the $\log_{10}(e_0) - \log_{10}(\rho_{p0})$ plane for three choices of the component masses respectively in the three panels: $m_A = m_B = 10 M_{\odot}$ and $m_A = m_B = 30 M_{\odot}$ within a fiducial multi-mass BH population (i.e. $p_0 = 0.5$, $\beta = 2.35$, and $m_{\text{BH,max}} = 30 M_{\odot}$), and for a single-mass BH population with $m_A = m_B = 10 M_{\odot}$. Clearly, the distributions are bounded by the boundaries derived in Figure 1 in Section 4.3. For low-mass EBBHs forming in a multi-mass BH population we find that a significant fraction of events form relatively close to the $\delta E_{\text{GW}} = E_{\text{fin}}$ boundary line. For massive EBBHs forming in a multi-mass BH population and for EBBHs forming in a single-mass BH population, we find that a significant fraction of events form at low ρ_{p0} close to the $\delta E_{\text{GW}} = E_{\text{fin}}$ boundary line, which corresponds to an approximately parabolic encounter. The merger rate distribution for a single-mass population is similar to the merger rate distribution for the heaviest components in a multi-mass distribution as shown by the bottom two panels in Figure 3.

The Monte Carlo samples show that EBBHs form typically with high eccentricities ($0.9 \lesssim e_0$), and ρ_{p0} ranges from $\sim 8-9$ up to $\sim 400-900$. The typical range of ρ_{p0} of GW capture sources can be understood using analytic arguments presented in Appendix B. Among mergers occurring at a fixed radius r , ρ_{p0} is distributed uniformly for $\rho_{p0} \leq \rho_{p0,\text{uni}}$

$$\rho_{p0,\text{uni}} = \left(\frac{85\pi\eta}{24\sqrt{2}} \right)^{2/7} v_{\text{max}}^{-4/7} = \left(\frac{85\pi\eta}{48\sqrt{2}} \right)^{2/7} \left(\frac{r}{M_{\text{SMBH}}} \right)^{2/7}. \quad (57)$$

Note that here the first term is unity (0.9952) for equal mass binaries with $\eta = 0.25$. If half of the events are located within $0.01 \text{ pc} \sim 5 \times 10^4 M_{\text{SgrA}^*}$, this implies a characteristic cutoff scale at $\rho_{p0,\text{uni}} \sim 22$. The cutoff scale $\rho_{p0,\text{uni}}$ depends on the mass of the binary system due to their different radial merger distributions shown in Figure 2. For the most massive BHs in a Milky Way-size nucleus, roughly 50% of them are located

⁸ Histograms are normalized by the total number of the data points.

Figure 3. Two-dimensional histograms of data points generated by the Monte Carlo code. The *top* and *bottom panels* correspond to $10M_{\odot} - 10M_{\odot}$ and $30M_{\odot} - 30M_{\odot}$ EBBHs forming in a fiducial multi-mass BH population with $dN/dm \propto m^{-2.35}$, $p_0 = 0.5$ and $m_{\text{BH,max}} = 30M_{\odot}$ and the *middle panel* corresponds to EBBHs forming in a single-mass BH population. We assumed a Milky Way-size nucleus in all cases. We simulated 10^9 binaries but here we represented those that did not interact with a third object before the merger phase of the EBBH evolution (the fraction of binaries interacting with a third object during the eccentric inspiral is generally negligible ($< 1\%$) in GNs). Histogram were normalized by the total number of the data points, and thus they serve as estimators for two-dimensional PDFs of EBBH merger events in the $\log_{10}(1 - e_0^2) - \log_{10}(\rho_{p0})$ plane. The dashed line at $\rho_{p0} \sim 41$ in the *top* and *middle panels*, and at $\rho_{p0} \sim 20$ in the *bottom panel* represents the lower limit of the aLIGO band (Equation 59), and we find in panels from top to bottom that about (41, 80, 56)% of EBBHs form within the aLIGO band. In case of the *middle* and *bottom panels*, formation regions are very similar to each other, which is due to the same profile of the PDF of EBBH merger rate inside the nucleus, see Figure 2 as an example.

within $4 \times 10^{-3} \text{ pc} \sim 2000 M_{\text{SgrA}^*}$ which implies a cutoff scale at $\rho_{p0,\text{uni}} \sim 9$, while roughly 50% of the least massive EBBHs are located within $1.2 \text{ pc} \sim 5.8 \times 10^6 M_{\text{SgrA}^*}$, which implies a cutoff scale at $\rho_{p0,\text{uni}} \sim 85$.

The characteristic scale of ρ_{p0} given by Equation (57) for a given v_{max} is applicable for an arbitrary host population. In globular clusters the escape velocity is much lower than in GN with a SMBH. Plugging in $v_{\text{max}} \sim 60 \text{ km/s}$ (30 km/s) gives a cutoff scale of $\rho_{p0,\text{uni}} = 160$ (230). Thus, a *smoking gun signature of GW capture events in high velocity dispersion environments (i.e. GN) is their small characteristic ρ_{p0} values below ~ 100 .*

We find that the inner cutoff of ρ_{p0} is insensitive to the component masses of the merging binary, the mass of the SMBH, and the mass distribution of the BH population. This is due to the fact that its leading order expression gives $\rho_{p0} \geq 8$ (see Section 4.3) independently of system parameters. However, the upper limit of ρ_{p0} is determined by the segment of boundary lines defined by criteria (III) and (IV) (see Figure 1, and it significantly depends on M_{SMBH} and the component masses m_A and m_B . Moreover, the results are weakly sensitive to the p_0 and β parameters of the BH mass distribution, and more sensitive to $m_{\text{BH,max}}$.

Figure 4 displays the one dimensional PDF of the initial pericenter distance and eccentricity respectively, by marginalizing the 2D distribution shown in Figure 3 over the other parameters for EBBH sources (cf. Figure 4 of O’Leary et al. 2009). Different lines represent the distribution of different component masses for merging binaries. Solid lines shows results for a fiducial multi-mass BH population with $dN/dm \propto m^{-2.35}$, $m_{\text{BH,max}} = 30M_{\odot}$, and $p_0 = 0.5$ in Equation (5).

The main findings of Figures 4, 5, and 6 are summarized as follows

- (A) Generally we find that at formation most sources have pericenter distances in the range $\rho_{p0} \sim 10 - 80$ and eccentricity $e_0 \sim 0.9 - 0.9999$. More massive EBBHs form with systematically lower ρ_{p0} and with less extreme e_0 (e.g. $\rho_{p0} \lesssim 20$ and $e_0 \sim 0.9$ for the heaviest BHs in the distribution). This is due to the fact that in a multi-mass BH population, more massive EBBHs form closer to the center of the nucleus (see Figure 2), thus w extends to higher values $2v_{\text{max}}(r)$ (Equation 6), and binary formation by GW capture implies $\rho_{p0} \propto w^{\beta}$ with $-4/7 \leq \beta \leq 0$ and $\epsilon_0 \propto w^{\gamma}$ with $0 \leq \gamma \leq 10/7$ (Equations 50 and 53).⁹
- (B) The maximum BH mass in the distribution $m_{\text{BH,max}}$ influences the PDF of ρ_{p0} and e_0 for different BH mass mergers significantly. However, the mass segregation parameter (assuming it is in the range $0.5 < p_0 < 0.6$) and the slope of the BH mass function (assuming the range $1 < \beta < 3$) does not influence these PDFs significantly. This result is consistent with analytic expectations presented in Section 5.1.
- (C) Both ρ_{p0} and ϵ_0 are somewhat lower for EBBHs of lower q at fixed M_{tot} , which arise due to the Equations (50) and (53) for ρ_{p0} and ϵ_0 , (where $\eta = q/(q+1)^2$).

⁹ The encounter cross section is typically dominated by gravitational focusing, which implies a uniform $P(\rho_{p0})$ distribution for isotropic distribution of relative velocity with a fixed magnitude w (Kocsis et al. 2006; O’Leary et al. 2009) in the range $0 \leq \rho_{p0} \leq k\eta^{2/7}w^{-4/7}$, where $k = (85\pi/6\sqrt{2})^{2/7}$. The decrease of $P(\rho_{p0})$ is due to the distribution of w in the GN.

Figure 4. PDF of ρ_{p0} (top panel) and $1-e_0^2$ (bottom panel) for different component-mass EBBHs forming in a Milky Way-size nucleus. Solid lines correspond to EBBHs forming in a fiducial multi-mass BH population with $dN/dm \propto m^{-2.35}$, $m_{\text{BH,max}} = 30M_{\odot}$, $p_0 = 0.5$ in Equation (5), and dashed-dotted lines correspond to EBBHs forming in a single-mass BH population. We find that more massive EBBHs have lower ρ_{p0} and e_0 , and EBBHs forming in a single-mass BH populations have lower ρ_{p0} and e_0 than similar EBBHs forming in a multi-mass BH population. Moreover, the PDF of ρ_{p0} and e_0 for EBBHs forming in a single-mass BH population are very similar to that of EBBHs formed by the most massive BHs of a multi-mass BH population, which is due to the same profile of the PDF of EBBH merger rate inside the nucleus (Figure 2). We find that both ρ_{p0} and e_0 are lower for binaries of lower q at fixed M_{tot} , and the discrepancy between PDFs of different mass ratio EBBHs increases with M_{tot} .

However since $\rho_{p0,\text{uni}} \propto \eta^{2/7}$, this dependence is rather weak. Moreover, the difference between the PDFs of EBBHs with different mass ratios increases with M_{tot} due to the M_{tot} dependence of the minimum radius, r_{min}^{AB} , and the corresponding increased value of w for increasing M_{tot} .

- (D) In simulations with different M_{SMBH} (Figure 5), we find that EBBHs form with lower ρ_{p0} and e_0 around more massive SMBHs independently of the binary component masses and the BH population parameters. This is due to the fact that the average relative velocity with which BHs form EBBHs in the GN increases with M_{SMBH} (Figure 12). Thus, by considering Equations (53) and (50) we find that both e_0 and ρ_{p0} systematically decrease with M_{SMBH} .
- (E) $10M_{\odot} - 10M_{\odot}$ EBBHs form with lower ρ_{p0} and e_0 in a single-mass BH population than in a multi-mass BH

Figure 5. An example of how different SMBH masses influence the PDF of ρ_{p0} (top panel) and $1-e_0^2$ (bottom panel). Results are shown for $10M_{\odot} - 10M_{\odot}$ EBBHs forming in a fiducial multi-mass BH population with $dN/dm \propto m^{-2.35}$, $m_{\text{BH,max}} = 30M_{\odot}$, and $p_0 = 0.5$ in Equation (5).

population. Moreover, the PDF of ρ_{p0} and e_0 are very similar for EBBHs forming in a single-mass BH population and EBBHs formed by the most massive BHs in a multi-mass BH population, which is due to the similarity between the corresponding EBBH merger rate distributions and $r_{\text{min}}^{A,B}$ values (Figure 2).

Eccentric binaries emit a GW signal with a broad spectrum of frequencies. The peak gravitational wave frequency associated with the harmonic which leads to the maximal emission of GW radiation can be estimated as

$$f_{\text{GW}} = \frac{2(1+e)^{1.1954}}{(1-e^2)^{3/2}} \frac{M_{\text{tot}}^{1/2}}{2\pi a^{3/2}(e)} \quad (58)$$

Wen (2003). Here f_{GW} defines the GW frequency related to the GW signal of a compact binary system with M_{tot} and e . We assume that those EBBHs form within the aLIGO band in the $e_0 - \rho_{p0}$ plane for which f_{GW} exceeds the $f_{\text{aLIGO}} = 10\text{Hz}$ frequency limit. Since EBBHs form with $e_0 \sim 1$, therefore f_{GW} can be expressed in terms of ρ_{p0} as $f_{\text{GW},0} = (2^{0.3046} \pi M_{\text{tot}} \rho_{p0}^{3/2})^{-1}$ after combining Equation (58) with Equation (25). Thus, those EBBHs form within the LIGO band for

Figure 6. An example of how different multi-mass BH population parameters influence the PDF of ρ_{p0} (top panel) and $1 - e_0^2$ (bottom panel). Results are shown for $10M_\odot - 10M_\odot$ EBBHs forming in a Milky Way-size nucleus. Solid thick lines correspond to a fiducial multi-mass BH population with $dN/dm \propto m^{-2.35}$, $m_{\text{BH,max}} = 30M_\odot$, and $p_0 = 0.5$ in Equation (5), while dash-dotted and dotted lines correspond to modified parameter values for a multi-mass BH population as shown in the legend of the top panel. Consistently with analytic expectations, only $m_{\text{BH,max}}$ influences significantly the PDF of ρ_{p0} and $1 - e_0^2$.

which ρ_{p0} does not exceed the limit

$$\begin{aligned} \rho_{p0,\text{aLIGO}} &= (2^{0.3046} \pi M_{\text{tot}} f_{\text{aLIGO}})^{-2/3} \\ &= 40.9 \left(\frac{M_{\text{tot}}}{20M_\odot} \right)^{-2/3} \left(\frac{f_{\text{aLIGO}}}{10\text{Hz}} \right)^{-2/3}. \end{aligned} \quad (59)$$

Note that this lies in the expected range of the ρ_{p0} distribution of GW capture sources given in Equation (57).

An important question for GW detections is the fraction of objects that are eccentric when they emit GWs in the aLIGO band. In Tables 1 and 2 we show the fraction of highly eccentric GW capture sources that form with a GW spectrum that peaks above 10 Hz (F_{aLIGO}), the fraction of EBBHs that have $e > 0.1$ when the GW spectrum first peaks above 10 Hz, and the fraction of EBBHs that have $e > 0.1$ when the binary reaches the LSO for various binary and SMBH masses. Depending on the component masses and the SMBH mass, we find that in a source population with $m_{\text{BH,max}} = 30M_\odot$ ($m_{\text{BH,max}} = 80M_\odot$) $F_{\text{res}>0.1} = 68\% - 99\%$ ($41\% - 99\%$) of the EBBHs are at least moderately eccentric with $e > 0.1$ when the spectrum first peaks above 10 Hz (see discussion in Section 5.3), and $F_{\text{aLIGO}} = 25\% - 64\%$ ($9\% - 67\%$) of highly ec-

Table 1

The fraction of EBBHs having residual eccentricities larger than 0.1 when their GW signals enter the aLIGO band ($F_{\text{res}>0.1}$), of EBBHs forming within the aLIGO band (F_{aLIGO}), and of EBBHs having eccentricities larger than 0.1 at the last stable orbit ($F_{\text{LSO}>0.1}$). We use *Single* to denote rows corresponding to a single-mass BH population, otherwise a fiducial multi-mass BH population is considered with $dN/dm \propto m^{-2.35}$, $m_{\text{BH,max}} = 30M_\odot$, and $p_0 = 0.5$ in Equation (5), and M_{SgrA^*} denotes the mass of the SMBH for a Milky Way-size nucleus. Systems were evolved from their initial orbit using the evolution equations of Peters (1964). F_{aLIGO} increases with M_{SMBH} at fixed component masses for both type of BH populations, which arises due to the decrease of ρ_{p0} against M_{SMBH} . Consequently, a lower-and-lower fraction of EBBHs are needed to evolve from their initial orbit up until their GW frequency f_{GW} (Wen 2003) reaches the aLIGO band, which increases $F_{\text{res}>0.1}$, and $F_{e_{\text{LSO}>0.1}}$ with M_{SMBH} as well. Moreover, we find that $F_{\text{res}>0.1}$ (F_{aLIGO} , and $F_{\text{LSO}>0.1}$) is higher for EBBHs of lower q at fixed M_{tot} , and the discrepancy between $F_{\text{res}>0.1}$ (F_{aLIGO} , and $F_{\text{LSO}>0.1}$) of different q increases with M_{tot} .

$m_A - m_B$ [M_\odot]	M_{SMBH} [M_\odot]	$F_{\text{res}>0.1}$	F_{aLIGO}	$F_{\text{LSO}>0.1}$
5-5	10^5	88%	35%	3%
10-10	10^5	69%	25%	4%
10-10 (Single)	10^5	96%	78%	35%
5-15	10^5	73%	27%	4%
10-30	10^5	68%	32%	12%
20-20	10^5	69%	31%	12%
30-30	10^5	84%	51%	32%
5-5	10^6	96%	48%	5%
10-10	10^6	85%	35%	7%
10-10 (Single)	10^6	97%	79%	36%
5-15	10^6	87%	36%	6%
10-30	10^6	78%	38%	15%
20-20	10^6	80%	38%	16%
30-30	10^6	86%	54%	36%
5-5	M_{SgrA^*}	98%	58%	6%
10-10	M_{SgrA^*}	91%	41%	7%
10-10 (Single)	M_{SgrA^*}	98%	80%	37%
5-15	M_{SgrA^*}	93%	44%	7%
10-30	M_{SgrA^*}	81%	43%	17%
20-20	M_{SgrA^*}	82%	41%	17%
30-30	M_{SgrA^*}	88%	56%	37%
5-5	10^7	99%	64%	7%
10-10	10^7	88%	45%	8%
10-10 (Single)	10^7	99%	81%	38%
5-15	10^7	96%	49%	9%
10-30	10^7	88%	46%	18%
20-20	10^7	86%	43%	18%
30-30	10^7	90%	57%	38%

centric sources form in the aLIGO band (these sources have $e_0 > 0.9$, see Figure 7). However, most of these sources circularize to below $e < 0.1$ by the time the binary approaches the last stable orbit. We find that the fraction of sources among this formation channel with $e > 0.1$ at the last stable orbit is between $F_{\text{LSO}>0.1} = 3\% - 38\%$ ($3\% - 36\%$) for EBBHs forming in a source population with $m_{\text{BH,max}} = 30M_\odot$ ($m_{\text{BH,max}} = 80M_\odot$) shown in Table 1 (2). In particular, sources that remain eccentric until the LSO have masses comparable to the maximum BH mass in the cluster, while lower mass binaries are systematically more circular near the LSO. We discuss F_{aLIGO} and $F_{\text{LSO}>0.1}$ separately in Sections 5.3 and 5.4 below.

To check the robustness of these predictions we show the fractional rates of eccentric sources for different BH mass function exponents β , and mass segregation parameter p_0 in Table 3. We find that (i) F_{aLIGO} is significantly influenced by $m_{\text{BH,max}}$, and slightly by p_0 and β ; (ii) F_{aLIGO} is higher for EBBHs of lower q at fixed M_{tot} ; (iii) F_{aLIGO} increases with

Table 2Same as Table 1, but for a source population with $m_{\text{BH,max}} = 80M_{\odot}$.

$m_A - m_B [M_{\odot}]$	$M_{\text{SMBH}} [M_{\odot}]$	$F_{\text{res}>0.1}$	F_{aLIGO}	$F_{\text{LSO}>0.1}$
5–5	10^5	89%	37%	3%
10–10	10^5	68%	24%	4%
5–15	10^5	70%	24%	4%
10–30	10^5	51%	16%	5%
20–20	10^5	50%	9%	4%
30–30	10^5	43%	13%	6%
50–50	10^5	41%	11%	10%
20–80	10^5	56%	13%	12%
60–60	10^5	50%	13%	15%
50–70	10^5	49%	12%	14%
70–70	10^5	67%	11%	26%
80–80	10^5	63%	12%	29%
5–5	10^6	96%	47%	5%
10–10	10^6	81%	29%	5%
5–15	10^6	86%	30%	5%
10–30	10^6	66%	21%	7%
20–20	10^6	63%	13%	6%
30–30	10^6	55%	16%	7%
50–50	10^6	58%	14%	12%
20–80	10^6	51%	15%	13%
60–60	10^6	57%	15%	18%
50–70	10^6	55%	14%	17%
70–70	10^6	62%	15%	28%
80–80	10^6	68%	15%	34%
5–5	10^7	99%	67%	7%
10–10	10^7	94%	40%	7%
5–15	10^7	96%	43%	8%
10–30	10^7	79%	29%	10%
20–20	10^7	78%	18%	8%
30–30	10^7	69%	21%	10%
50–50	10^7	61%	16%	15%
20–80	10^7	67%	20%	18%
60–60	10^7	68%	18%	22%
50–70	10^7	63%	17%	21%
70–70	10^7	66%	18%	29%
80–80	10^7	72%	18%	36%

Table 3

Same as Table 1 for $10M_{\odot} - 10M_{\odot}$ EBBHs, but for different values of the parameters shown in the first column. We find that only $m_{\text{BH,max}}$ influences the results significantly: higher maximum BH masses in the cluster lead to much lower LSO eccentricities among mergers with fixed binary component masses.

Parameter	$F_{\text{res}>0.1}$	F_{aLIGO}	$F_{\text{LSO}>0.1}$
standard	91%	41%	7%
$\beta = 1$	91%	41%	7%
$\beta = 3$	91%	41%	7%
$m_{\text{BH,max}} = 10M_{\odot}$	98%	80%	37%
$m_{\text{BH,max}} = 15M_{\odot}$	94%	59%	16%
$m_{\text{BH,max}} = 80M_{\odot}$	90%	35%	6%
$p_0 = 0.6$	92%	43%	8%

M_{SMBH} ; and (iv) F_{aLIGO} is lower for EBBHs forming in a single-mass BH population than similar EBBHs forming in a multi-mass BH population. These results may be explained by arguments listed in (B), (C), (D), and (E) above. However, F_{aLIGO} is not similar for EBBHs forming in a single-mass BH population and EBBHs formed by the most massive BHs in a multi-mass BH population, and does not systematically increase with the component masses because $\rho_{p0,\text{aLIGO}}$ depends on the component masses as well.

Figure 7. The PDF of residual eccentricity for different component-mass EBBHs when their emitted GW signals first peak at 10Hz or when they form at a higher frequency (cf. Figures 4 and 8 for the initial and final eccentricity distribution). We assume EBBHs forming through GW capture in a Milky Way-size nucleus. Different lines correspond to different component masses in a multi-mass population and in a single-mass population as in Figure 4. The sharp peaks beyond $e_{\text{res}} \sim 0.9$ correspond to EBBHs forming within the aLIGO band. For masses $(10M_{\odot} - 10M_{\odot}, 20M_{\odot} - 20M_{\odot}, 30M_{\odot} - 30M_{\odot}, 10M_{\odot} - 30M_{\odot})$, respectively, in a multi-mass BH population, we find that (41, 41, 56, 43)% of EBBHs form in the aLIGO band. This number is 80% for a single-mass BH population. We find that residual eccentricities at 10Hz are larger than 0.1 for (91, 81, 88, 86)% of $(10M_{\odot} - 10M_{\odot}, 20M_{\odot} - 20M_{\odot}, 30M_{\odot} - 30M_{\odot}, 10M_{\odot} - 30M_{\odot})$ EBBHs and 98% in a single-mass BH population (see Table 1).

Additionally, our calculations show that only a negligible fraction ($\lesssim 1\%$) of the EBBHs interact with a third object during the eccentric inspiral. This implies that analytic expressions can be derived to determine the two-dimensional PDFs in the $\epsilon_0 - \rho_{p0}$ plane as shown in Appendix B.4, and similarly for the marginalized 1D ρ_{p0} and ϵ_0 distributions, (Appendix B.5 and B.6).

5.3. Eccentricity distribution when the GW signal first enters the aLIGO band

We evolve systems from their initial orbital parameters using the evolution equations of Peters (1964). For many systems the binary has a GW frequency in the aLIGO band at formation. However systems that form outside of the aLIGO band may also enter the aLIGO band before merger. Figure 7 displays examples for the PDF of residual eccentricity e_{res} when the peak GW signal frequency f_{GW} (Equation 58) first reaches 10Hz. We find in all cases that (i) a sharp peak occurs in the PDF at $e_{\text{res}} \sim 1$, which corresponds to EBBHs forming within the aLIGO band at $f > 10\text{Hz}$; (ii) a peak forms at moderately small (0.05–0.15) eccentricities. The latter (ii) can be explained as follows: e_{res} can be obtained by solving the equation $f_{\text{aLIGO}} = f_{\text{GW}}$, which can be rewritten as

$$f_{\text{aLIGO}} = \left[(1 + e_{\text{res}})^{0.3046} \pi M_{\text{tot}} \rho_p^{3/2} (e_{\text{res}}, e_0, \rho_{p0}) \right]^{-1}, \quad (60)$$

where ρ_p is given by Equation (28). By definition $e_{\text{res}} \equiv e_0$ for EBBHs with $\rho_{p0} \leq \rho_{p0,\text{aLIGO}}$ (Equation 59). Solving Equation (60) for e_{res} by setting $\rho_{p0} \geq \rho_{p0,\text{aLIGO}}$, we find that e_{res} drops off quickly at $\rho_{p0} \sim \rho_{p0,\text{aLIGO}}$ and its tail starts at $e_{\text{res}} \sim 0.5$, which implies that a significant fraction of EBBHs with $\rho_{p0} \geq \rho_{p0,\text{aLIGO}}$ have $e_{\text{res}} \leq 0.5$ when they enter the aLIGO band. Furthermore, EBBHs that formed with $\rho_{p0} \gtrsim \rho_{p0,\text{aLIGO}}$ exhibit a peak in the PDF of e_{res} at $e_{\text{res}} \sim 0.05 - 0.15$.

The total fraction of EBBHs with residual eccentricities larger than 0.1 when their emitted GW signals first exceed

10Hz ($F_{\text{res}>0.1}$) are presented in Tables 1-3 for various values of fixed component masses. We find that (i) $F_{\text{res}>0.1}$ is significantly influenced by $m_{\text{BH,max}}$ but it is not sensitive to the mass function exponent β and the mass segregation parameter p_0 ; (ii) $F_{\text{res}>0.1}$ is higher for EBBHs of lower q at fixed M_{tot} , and the difference between $F_{\text{res}>0.1}$ of different q becomes more substantial with increasing M_{tot} ; (iii) $F_{\text{res}>0.1}$ increases with M_{SMBH} ; and (iv) $F_{\text{res}>0.1}$ is lower for EBBHs forming in a single-mass BH population than for similar EBBHs forming in a multi-mass BH population. These findings arise due to (B), (C), (D), and (E) because ρ_{p0} is the only free parameter that determines e_{res} when the component masses are fixed. However, $F_{\text{res}>0.1}$ is not similar for EBBHs forming in a single-mass BH population and EBBHs formed by the most massive BHs in a multi-mass BH population, and does not increase systematically with the component masses because e_{res} depends on the component masses as well.

Overall we find that in a source population with $m_{\text{BH,max}} = 30M_{\odot}$ ($m_{\text{BH,max}} = 80M_{\odot}$), at least $F_{\text{res}>0.1} = 65\% - 86\%$ ($38\% - 58\%$) of EBBHs have residual eccentricities larger than 0.1 when their GW signals first reach 10Hz or form with higher frequencies. The actual value within this range is generally set by the binary component-masses, the mass segregation parameter, the exponent of the BH mass function, and $M_{\text{SMBH}} \in [10^5 M_{\odot}, 10^7 M_{\odot}]$. Larger values correspond to higher M_{SMBH} . Similarly, for in a single-mass BH population, we find that the fraction of sources with a residual eccentricity is higher: $F_{\text{res}>0.1} \geq 96\%$ as shown in Tables 1 and 2.

5.4. Eccentricity distribution at the last stable orbit

Let us now examine the distribution of the final eccentricity at LSO, shown in Figure 8. We show the results for the same choices of parameters as in Figure 7. These numerical results show that (i) higher e_{LSO} values correspond to higher mass BHs in the distribution; (ii) the PDF of e_{LSO} is affected significantly by $m_{\text{BH,max}}$ but it is not influenced significantly by the mass distribution exponent and mass-segregation parameters β and p_0 ; (iv) the M_{tot} influences the result more significantly than the mass ratio, a lower q shifts the e_{LSO} distribution to slightly lower values, as shown; (v) EBBHs form with higher e_{LSO} around more massive SMBHs (Tables 1 and 2) (v) EBBHs forming in a single-mass BH populations have an e_{LSO} distribution similar to that of the most massive EBBHs in a multi-mass BH population. Since e_{LSO} is a decreasing function of ρ_{p0} (Equation 32) these results may be explained respectively by arguments for the distribution of ρ_{p0} listed in (A), (B), (C), (D), and (E) above.

The characteristic scale of e_{LSO} may be understood using the characteristic value for ρ_{p0} given by Equation (57) and the relation between ρ_{p0} and e_{LSO} given by Equation (32). For mergers at a fixed radius r , the distribution of ρ_{p0} is flat for $\rho_{p0} \leq \rho_{p0,\text{uni}}$, implying that $P(e_{\text{LSO}}) \propto e_{\text{LSO}}^{-8/5}$ for $e_{\text{LSO}} \gtrsim e_{\text{LSO,peak}}$, where

$$\begin{aligned} e_{\text{LSO,peak}} &\approx 0.2682 \rho_{p0,\text{uni}}^{8/5} \\ &= 0.0252 (4\eta)^{-16/35} \left(\frac{v_{\text{max}}}{1,000 \text{ km/s}} \right)^{32/35} \\ &= 0.2703 (4\eta)^{-16/35} \left(\frac{r}{1000 M_{\text{SMBH}}} \right)^{-16/35}. \end{aligned} \quad (61)$$

The distribution on a logarithmic scale follows $P(\ln e_{\text{LSO}}) = e_{\text{LSO}} P(e_{\text{LSO}}) \propto e_{\text{LSO}}^{-3/5}$ for values $e_{\text{LSO}} \gtrsim e_{\text{LSO,peak}}$. The char-

Figure 8. *Top panel:* The distribution of eccentricity at the LSO (e_{LSO} , cf. Figures 4 and 7 for the initial eccentricity distribution and that at 10 Hz). Different lines correspond to different component masses in a multi-mass population and in a single-mass population as in Figure 4. In a multi-mass population, more massive EBBHs have systematically higher e_{LSO} , and EBBHs forming in a single-mass BH populations have higher e_{LSO} than similar EBBHs forming in a multi-mass BH population. *Middle panel:* The influence of different assumptions on the results. We vary the mass function exponent β , the maximum mass of the multi-mass BH population $m_{\text{BH,max}}$, and the mass segregation parameter p_0 . We find that only $m_{\text{BH,max}}$ influences the distribution of e_{LSO} significantly. *Bottom Panel:* The M_{SMBH} dependence of e_{LSO} -distribution (cf. Figure 5 for e_0).

characteristic values of e_{LSO} may be determined for GW capture events with different masses similar to the discussion below Equation (57). For the most massive EBBHs, we find that roughly 50% of them are within $r \sim 4 \times 10^{-3}$ pc in a Milky Way-size nucleus, which corresponds to $2000 M_{\text{SgrA}^*}$, where $e_{\text{LSO,peak}}$ is ~ 0.19 . However for the least massive EBBHs with $m_A = m_B = 5 M_\odot$, 50% of them are within $1.2 \text{ pc} \sim 5.8 \times 10^6 M_{\text{SgrA}^*}$ for which $e_{\text{LSO,peak}} \sim 0.005$. Thus the peak of the e_{LSO} -distribution is high for heavy members of a given population because they are in the close vicinity of the SMBH, while the low mass members have a much lower e_{LSO} since they are typically much farther out. Thus, the measurement of the e_{LSO} -distribution for different masses may be used to detect the mass-segregation of the sources within their host environment.

Conversely, solving Equation (61) for the velocity dispersion $\sigma \sim v_{\text{max}}/\sqrt{2}$, gives

$$\sigma \sim 258 \frac{\text{km}}{\text{s}} (4\eta)^{1/2} \left(\frac{e_{\text{LSO,peak}}}{0.01} \right)^{35/32}. \quad (62)$$

Thus, the measurement of the peak eccentricity of a GW capture binary at LSO gives an estimate of the typical velocity dispersion of the source environment.

In all of our simulations we have neglected those encounters for which BHs make a direct head-on collision without forming an EBBH (i.e. $\rho_{\text{p0}} \geq 8$ in all cases, see Figure 4). This causes the PDFs of e_{LSO} to cut off at $e_{\text{LSO}} \sim 0.23$ (Figure 8).

By examining the e_{LSO} -distribution for various SMBH mass, BH mass, and BH population parameters, we find that approximately $\lesssim 71\%$, $\lesssim 14\%$, $\lesssim 0.2\%$, of the most massive EBBHs have eccentricities lower than 0.1 , 10^{-2} , 10^{-3} at LSO, respectively. The corresponding numbers for the lowest-mass EBBHs are respectively $\lesssim 97\%$, $\lesssim 66\%$, $\lesssim 4\%$. In case of a single-mass BH population, approximately $\lesssim 60\%$, $\lesssim 16\%$, $\lesssim 0.24\%$ of EBBHs have eccentricities lower than 0.1 , 10^{-2} , 10^{-3} at LSO, respectively, for SMBH masses between $10^5 M_\odot$ and $10^7 M_\odot$.¹⁰ Overall, we find that a negligible fraction of EBBHs have eccentricities lower than 10^{-3} at LSO over the considered ranges of BH mass, SMBH mass, and BH population parameter ranges. Note that for initially highly eccentric precessing BH binaries, the expected relative measurement accuracy of e_{LSO} is $\lesssim 5\%$ for $30 M_\odot - 30 M_\odot$ ($10 M_\odot - 10 M_\odot$) precessing EBBHs with $\rho_{\text{p0}} \leq 80$ ($\rho_{\text{p0}} \leq 100$) for the aLIGO-AdV-KAGRA detector network (Gondán et al. 2017). This implies that the predicted range of e_{LSO} may typically be distinguished from zero in future GW detections.

Note that the distribution of e_{LSO} has been previously calculated in O’Leary et al. (2009) for a single-mass population. We find two main differences with respect to those results. First, the PDF peaks at a slightly higher value ~ 0.2 for a single-mass distribution instead of ~ 0.1 in O’Leary et al. (2009), and it drops off quickly beyond the peak instead of taking values at higher eccentricities. The somewhat higher e_{LSO} arises due to the fact that the minimum radius at which the formation of EBBHs is still considered is about 4.5 times lower than that in O’Leary et al. (2009), which implies higher w , thus lower ρ_{p0} , and thereby larger e_{LSO} . Note that we assumed a slightly more massive SMBH mass than O’Leary et al. (2009), which increases the values of e_{LSO} . In our case,

¹⁰ Note that these results correspond to $10^5 M_\odot$ SMBHs because EBBHs with lowest e_{LSO} values form in these SMBHs (Section 5.4) The results are insensitive to the upper bound of the SMBH masses.

the PDF of e_{LSO} drops off quickly beyond the peak of the distribution at $e_{\text{LSO}} \sim 0.23$ because we have neglected those encounters for which BHs coalesce before EBBHs form (i.e. $\rho_{\text{p0}} \leq 8$ in all cases, see Sections 4.3 and 5.2 for details), while those binaries are included in the plotted e_{LSO} -distributions in O’Leary et al. (2009). However, in a multi-mass distribution, the peak e_{LSO} values are even lower than in O’Leary et al. (2009) as shown in Figure 8.

5.5. Total mass and mass-ratio distributions

Let us now examine the two-dimensional distribution of the merger rate in the $q - M_{\text{tot}}$ plane, $\langle \partial^2 \Gamma / \partial M_{\text{tot}} \partial q \rangle$, which affects the mass dependent detection rates. This is derived by integrating $\partial^3 \Gamma / \partial r \partial m_A \partial m_B$ (Equation 54) over the allowed range of r from $r_{\text{min}}^{A,B}$ to r_{max} for each fixed m_A and m_B component masses. In Appendix B.7, we show that this leads to an analytical expression¹¹. Up to a constant normalization factor,

$$P(m_A, m_B) \approx \eta^{\frac{2}{3}-\beta} M_{\text{tot}}^{2-2\beta} \left(1 - \frac{2}{3} \bar{M}_{\text{tot}} + \frac{4\eta}{9} \bar{M}_{\text{tot}}^2 \right) \frac{1 - \Lambda \bar{M}_{\text{tot}}^{-\frac{11}{14}}}{\frac{11}{14} - \bar{M}_{\text{tot}}} \quad (63)$$

if $m_{\text{BH,min}} \leq m_{A,B} \leq m_{\text{BH,max}}$, and zero otherwise, where we introduced the Coulomb logarithm¹²

$$\ln \Lambda = \ln \frac{r_{\text{max}}}{r_{\text{min}}^{A,B}}, \quad (64)$$

and \bar{M}_{tot} for the dimensionless total mass

$$\bar{M}_{\text{tot}} = p_0 \frac{M_{\text{tot}}}{m_{\text{BH,max}}}, \quad (65)$$

where $p_0 \sim 0.5$ (Equation 5) for which $m_{\text{BH,min}}/m_{\text{BH,max}} \leq \bar{M}_{\text{tot}} \leq 1$.

The likelihood¹³ of merger for any two given BHs in the cluster with mass m_A and m_B is proportional to $P(m_A, m_B)$ divided by the prior probability proportional to $\mathcal{F}(m_A)\mathcal{F}(m_B) \propto m_A^{-\beta} m_B^{-\beta} = \eta^{-\beta} M_{\text{tot}}^{-2\beta}$, which gives

$$\mathcal{L}(m_A, m_B) \approx \eta^{\frac{2}{3}} M_{\text{tot}}^2 \left(1 - \frac{2}{3} \bar{M}_{\text{tot}} + \frac{4\eta}{9} \bar{M}_{\text{tot}}^2 \right) \frac{1 - \Lambda \bar{M}_{\text{tot}}^{-\frac{11}{14}}}{\frac{11}{14} - \bar{M}_{\text{tot}}} \quad (66)$$

if $m_{\text{BH,min}} \leq m_{A,B} \leq m_{\text{BH,max}}$, and zero otherwise.

Recently Kocsis et al. (2017) have introduced a useful indicator¹⁴ to distinguish different source populations:

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha &= -M_{\text{tot}}^2 \frac{\partial \ln P(m_A, m_B)}{\partial m_A \partial m_B} \\ &= \frac{10}{7} - \frac{4}{9} \bar{M}_{\text{tot}}^2 \frac{\left(1 + \frac{4}{3} \bar{M}_{\text{tot}} - \frac{8}{9} \bar{M}_{\text{tot}}^2 \right)}{\left(1 - \frac{2}{3} \bar{M}_{\text{tot}} + \frac{1}{9} \bar{m}_A \bar{m}_B \right)^2} - \frac{\bar{M}_{\text{tot}}^2}{\left(\bar{M}_{\text{tot}} - \frac{11}{14} \right)^2} \\ &\quad + \frac{\bar{M}_{\text{tot}}^2 \Lambda \bar{M}_{\text{tot}}^{-\frac{11}{14}} \ln^2 \Lambda}{\left[1 - \Lambda \bar{M}_{\text{tot}}^{-\frac{11}{14}} \right]^2}, \end{aligned} \quad (67)$$

if $m_{\text{BH,min}} \leq m_{A,B} \leq m_{\text{BH,max}}$, and zero otherwise. Here $\bar{m}_{A,B} = 2p_0 m_{A,B}/m_{\text{BH,max}}$, which satisfies $\bar{m}_{A,B} \leq 1$ for $p_0 = 0.5$. The

¹¹ This expression includes GW captures and direct head-on collisions. See Equation (B45) for the case neglecting head-on collision.

¹² In the following expressions, we neglect the possible mass dependence of Λ .

¹³ i.e. conditional probability

¹⁴ not to be confused with the number density exponent α in Equation (8)

α parameter is universal, in that it is independent of the underlying BH mass function. This is a monotonically decreasing function of \bar{M}_{tot} for $\ln \Lambda < 11$, ranging between $1.42 \geq \alpha \geq -23.6 + (\Lambda^{3/28} - \Lambda^{-3/28})^{-1} \ln^2 \Lambda$ for $0 < \bar{M}_{\text{tot}} \leq 1$ for equal mass mergers and $1.42 \geq \alpha \geq -26.1 + (\Lambda^{3/28} - \Lambda^{-3/28})^{-1} \ln^2 \Lambda$ for very unequal mass mergers. In particular for $\ln \Lambda = 7$, a reasonable value of the Coulomb logarithm, we get $\alpha = -5.5$ for the heaviest BHs in the population and $\alpha = 1.4$ for the lightest BHs. The value of α is different for other source populations: $\alpha \sim 4$ for BH mergers in globular clusters (O’Leary et al. 2016), $\alpha = 1$ for primordial BH binaries formed in the early universe (Kocsis et al. 2017), and $\alpha = 10/7 = 1.43$ for primordial BHs formed in dark matter halos through GW capture¹⁵ (Bird et al. 2016).

Next we change variables from m_A and m_B to q and M_{tot} using the Jacobi determinant $\partial^3 \Gamma / \partial r \partial M_{\text{tot}} \partial q = J \partial^3 \Gamma / \partial r \partial m_A \partial m_B$, where $J = M_{\text{tot}}(1+q)^{-2}$ (see Equation (B49) in Appendix B.7)

$$P(M_{\text{tot}}, q) \approx q^{\frac{2}{3}-\beta} M_{\text{tot}}^{3-2\beta} \left(1 - \frac{2}{3} \bar{M}_{\text{tot}} + \frac{4\eta}{9} \bar{M}_{\text{tot}}^2 \right) \times \frac{(1+q)^{2\beta-\frac{18}{7}}}{\left(\frac{11}{14} - \bar{M}_{\text{tot}}\right)} \left[1 - \left(\frac{r_{\text{min}}^{A,B}}{r_{\text{max}}} \right)^{\frac{11}{14} - \bar{M}_{\text{tot}}} \right] \quad (68)$$

if $m_{\text{BH},\text{min}} \leq M_{\text{tot}}/(1+q) \leq m_{\text{BH},\text{max}}$ and $m_{\text{BH},\text{min}} \leq M_{\text{tot}}q/(1+q) \leq m_{\text{BH},\text{max}}$, and zero otherwise. These analytical results correspond to the distribution of all GW capture events which include direct collisions. The latter represents a small ($< 10\%$) fraction of the mergers. In the following we plot the probability distribution functions for EBBHs which avoid a direct collision.

The distribution of total detection rates from all galaxies is generally different from the merger rate density or the merger rate per a single nuclear star cluster, since the detection horizon d_{aLIGO} is different for different binary parameters. We calculate d_{aLIGO} for an eccentric inspiral waveform by calculating the signal-to-noise ratio following O’Leary et al. (2009) (see also Gondán et al. 2017). The detection rate distribution is then

$$\frac{\partial^2 \mathcal{R}_{\text{aLIGO}}}{\partial m_A \partial m_B} = \int_{\rho_{p0,\text{min}}}^{\rho_{p0,\text{max}}} d\rho_{p0} \int_{M_{\text{SMBH},\text{min}}}^{M_{\text{SMBH},\text{max}}} dM_{\text{SMBH}} V_{\text{aLIGO}} \frac{dn_{\text{gal}}}{dM_{\text{SMBH}}} \times \left\langle \frac{\partial^3 \Gamma}{\partial \rho_{p0} \partial m_A \partial m_B} \right\rangle, \quad (69)$$

where $dn_{\text{gal}}/dM_{\text{SMBH}}$ is the number density of galaxies with nuclear star clusters in the Universe which host an SMBH of mass M_{SMBH} , and $M_{\text{SMBH},\text{min}}$ and $M_{\text{SMBH},\text{max}}$ are the lower and upper bounds of the SMBH mass range of interest (Section 2.1). The detectable volume is $V_{\text{aLIGO}} = \frac{4}{3} \pi d_{\text{aLIGO}}^3$, if d_{aLIGO} is much less than the Hubble scale. We substitute Equation (54) for the partial event rates for different ρ_{p0} , and change variables from m_A and m_B to q and M_{tot} using the Jacobian as in Equation (68).

Figure 9 shows the two-dimensional PDF of merging EBBH event rates as a function of q and M_{tot} . The left panels show the distribution in a single Milky Way-size nucleus, and the right panels show the distribution for all galaxies in

the universe detectable by Advanced LIGO at design sensitivity. The top, middle, and bottom panels correspond to different BH mass function exponents $\beta = 1, 2.35$, and 3 , respectively, where the range of BH masses is assumed to be between $5M_{\odot} \leq m \leq 30M_{\odot}$. Since the results are not sensitive to the SMBH mass, the left panels display the distribution of the merger rate density in the Universe. Low binary total masses dominate the merger rate density if $\beta \gtrsim 3/2$ (see Equation (68)) and high binary masses close $M_{\text{tot}} \sim 2m_{\text{BH},\text{max}}$ dominate for a top-heavy mass function with $\beta = 1$. However, since aLIGO is more sensitive to higher mass mergers, the detection rate distributions shown in the right panels are skewed to higher total masses. This observational bias causes the detection rates to be highest at $M_{\text{tot}} \gtrsim m_{\text{BH},\text{max}}$ up to $2m_{\text{BH},\text{max}}$ for $\beta = 1$ and 2.35 . For $\beta = 3$, the distribution is peaked near $M_{\text{tot}} \sim m_{\text{BH},\text{max}}$ with unequal mass ratios. In all cases, equal mass mergers at the low end of the mass distribution $M_{\text{tot}} \sim 2m_{\text{BH},\text{min}}$ are highly disfavored for $\beta \leq 3$. Note that the mass ratio dependence of the detection rate for fixed M_{tot} is known analytically, since $d_{\text{aLIGO}} \propto \eta^{1/2} = q^{1/2}(1+q)^{-1}$ see Equation (C8) or O’Leary et al. (2009). Thus, $\partial^2 \mathcal{R}_{\text{aLIGO}} / \partial q \partial M_{\text{tot}} \propto q^{(25/14)-\beta} (1+q)^{2\beta-(39/7)}$.

Figure 10 shows the 1D marginalized distribution of the merger rate per single galaxy in a Milky Way-size galaxy¹⁶ as a function of chirp mass, binary total mass, and mass ratio, respectively. The mass ratio distribution of the merger rate density is widely distributed, with comparable component-mass mergers being a factor ~ 2 more likely than mergers with uneven component masses when $\beta \sim 1$, while uneven mass mergers are 20% more likely than comparable mass mergers for $\beta \sim 2.35$. Figure 10 also shows how the marginalized merger rate density depends on other model parameters as follows. Varying $m_{\text{BH},\text{max}}$ changes the boundaries of the $P(q, M_{\text{tot}})$ distributions. However, Equation (68) shows that $P(q, M_{\text{tot}})$ is otherwise independent of $m_{\text{BH},\text{max}}$ and the value of the mass segregation parameter p_0 other than for a rescaling of the M_{tot} mass units. The mass-distributions are also insensitive¹⁷ to M_{SMBH} , other than through r_{max} in Equation (68).

6. SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

In this paper, we determined the expected distribution of intrinsic parameters of merging black hole binaries that form in GN from initially unbound BHs due to GW emission during close encounters. The main intrinsic parameters describing these binaries are their component masses and the initial impact parameter and initial relative velocity before the encounter. Due to the large velocity dispersion in GN compared to objects in globular clusters, the galactic disk, or the halo, the objects in GN must approach one another at much smaller distances to form a binary. The implication is that the initial pericenter distance of the binary is relatively small when the initial eccentricity is beyond $e_0 > 0.9$. We extended the study of O’Leary et al. (2009) by calculating the eccentricity distribution for mergers among different component-masses in a multi-mass distribution, and examined the eccentricity distribution at three particular places during the evolution: at formation, at the instant when the peak GW frequency reaches

¹⁶ Due to the insensitivity to M_{SMBH} this is also the distribution of merger rate density.

¹⁷ Note that the absolute size of the merger rate is also insensitive to the SMBH mass as $M_{\text{SMBH}}^{3/28}$ (O’Leary et al. 2009; Kocsis & Levin 2012). We provide the SMBH mass dependent expressions in Appendix B.7.

¹⁵ Dark matter halos are collisionless systems, where mass segregation does not take place, so $\bar{M}_{\text{tot}} = 0$ in Equation (67).

Figure 9. Left panels show the two-dimensional PDF of merger rates of BH binaries that form due to GW emission in a single nuclear star cluster as a function of binary mass ratio and total mass. Right panels show the PDF of detection rates for Advanced LIGO at design sensitivity, which includes the mergers from all detectable galaxies in the Universe. Different rows of panels correspond to different BH mass functions $dN/dm = m^{-\beta}$, where $\beta = 1$ (top) 2.35 (middle), and 3 (bottom), respectively. The sharp boundaries are due to the assumption $5 M_{\odot} \leq m \leq 30 M_{\odot}$ for both BHs forming the binary. The segregation parameter (Equation 5) is $p_0 = 0.5$. For different maximum BH mass or p_0 assumptions (not shown) the merger rate distribution in a single cluster (left panel) is changed only through a rescaling of the M_{tot} axis (see Equation 68). The result are very weakly sensitive to the assumed SMBH mass.

Figure 10. The PDF of chirp mass (*top panel*), mass ratio (*middle panel*), and total mass (*bottom panel*) for merging EBBHs in a single Milky Way-size nucleus. We show how different parameters of a multi-mass BH population influence the PDFs. Solid thick lines correspond to our fiducial multi-mass BH population with $dN/dm \propto m^{-\beta}$ with $\beta = 2.35$, $p_0 = 0.5$, and $m_{\text{BH,max}} = 30M_{\odot}$. Other line styles show the distributions for other parameters as labeled in the legend of the top panel.

10 Hz, and at the LSO. We have also examined how different parameters describing a multi-mass BH distribution affect the distribution of merger rates as a function of masses, eccentricity, and initial pericenter distance. Many of our numerical results and the identified trends are validated by analytical expressions (Appendices B.4-B.6).

The main findings of this work can be summarized as fol-

lows:

- (i) We identified the region in the initial eccentricity–initial dimensionless pericenter distance plane where EBBHs may form through GW capture, and determined the two-dimensional PDF therein. The PDF of initial orbital parameters (Figure 4) shows that EBBHs form with high eccentricities ($0.9 \lesssim e_0 \lesssim 0.9999$), and the distribution of initial pericenter distance drops off quickly beyond $20 - 80M_{\text{tot}}$. The reason is that BHs form EBBHs with high relative velocities in nuclear star clusters around SMBHs (Figure 12). The eccentricity makes GW capture sources in these environments qualitatively different from other types of inspiraling GW sources.
- (ii) We determined the radial distribution from the central SMBH for GW capture sources with different component masses. We found that on a logarithmic radial scale the merger distribution rate is approximately independent of radius for the most massive components, $P(\ln r) \propto r^{-3/14}$ (Equation 55) between the radius of influence and the inner boundary set by GW-driven infall into the SMBH (i.e. ~ 3 pc and 10^{-4} pc, respectively in Milky-Way type galaxies). This implies that roughly 50% of the high-mass events are formed in the innermost 4×10^{-3} pc, and approximately 97% within 1.2 pc. The rate of GW capture sources among the least massive objects within the nuclear star cluster is skewed to higher radii on a logarithmic scale $P(\ln r) \propto r^{11/14}$ for $m \ll m_{\text{BH,max}}$ (Equation 55). These events are preferentially closer to the radius of influence; only 2% and roughly 50% of them are within 4×10^{-3} pc and 1.2 pc, respectively.
- (iii) We found that a negligible fraction ($1\% \lesssim$) of EBBHs interact with a third object during the eccentric inspiral.
- (iv) We determined how the distributions of orbital parameters depend on the mass of the central SMBH, on the binary masses, and on the parameters of the BH population (i.e. the highest possible BH mass, the exponent of the BH mass function, and the mass segregation parameter). We found that the initial pericenter distance systematically decreases with M_{SMBH} and the component masses, while the eccentricity at any stage of the time evolution systematically increases with M_{SMBH} and the component masses. As a consequence, more massive EBBHs around more massive SMBHs reach 10Hz frequency limit with higher eccentricity and have higher eccentricity at the LSO (Tables 1 and 2). The highest possible BH mass of the BH population affects the binary parameters of GW capture sources. Other parameters of the BH population does not influence the eccentricity distribution at 10Hz or at the LSO.
- (v) We found that most of the sources become circularized with eccentricities $e_{\text{LSO}} \sim 1\% - 10\%$ when they approach the last stable orbit. The fraction of sources with $e_{\text{LSO}} > 0.1$ is 3% – 30% if the maximum possible BH mass in the population is $30M_{\odot}$. This fraction of eccentric mergers among BHs with masses less than $30M_{\odot}$ is less than 7% if the highest mass in the population reaches $80M_{\odot}$ (Table 2). *Since the current GW detectors are only sensitive to the final part of the signal,*

the current non-detections of eccentricity are inconclusive with regards to the viability of this merger channel. Only 1 in 30 detections with $e_{\text{LSO}} > 0.1$ may be expected if the heaviest stellar BH mass in galactic nuclei is $80M_{\odot}$. However, the heaviest BHs in the distribution have higher eccentricities: 29%–36% of sources have $e_{\text{LSO}} > 0.1$. Their detection may require algorithms sensitive to non-circular orbit waveform features.

- (vi) A negligible fraction of EBBHs have eccentricities at LSO lower than 10^{-3} (Figure 8). In a companion paper, Gondán et al. (2017), we have shown that the expected relative measurement accuracy of e_{LSO} for the aLIGO-AdV-KAGRA GW detector network is $\lesssim 5\%$ when EBBHs form with relatively small ρ_{p0} values¹⁸. Other binary formation and evolution channels typically produce binaries with eccentricities at or below 10^{-3} when their GW signals enter the aLIGO band (Kowalska et al. 2011; Cholis et al. 2016; Rodriguez et al. 2016a,b; Silsbee & Tremaine 2017). *The measurement of eccentricity for a BH merger will be a smoking gun signature of sources in high velocity dispersion environments such as in the inner regions of galactic nuclei (Equation 62).*
- (vii) The prospects for detecting eccentric mergers are expected to improve significantly with the ongoing detector upgrades. We found that the fraction of sources with an eccentricity larger than 0.1 at peak GW frequency of 10 Hz is 41%–86% (Tables 1 and 2). *Thus, when Advanced LIGO and VIRGO reach their design sensitivity at 10 Hz, more than 1 in 2 sources will be initially eccentric in the detector band for this binary formation channel.*
- (viii) We conclude that Advanced LIGO/VIRGO detections may confirm or rule out this binary formation channel. However, algorithms using circular binary templates will be ineffective for the majority of sources in searching for GW signals of EBBHs forming through GW capture in GNs. This especially affects the heaviest BHs, since they are the most eccentric among this source population. The current GW detection limits of the heaviest black holes (Abbott et al. 2017d; Fishbach & Holz 2017) may be impacted by the inefficiency of the applied search algorithms to eccentric sources.
- (ix) We determined the PDFs of merger rates in single nuclear star clusters in terms of component-masses (i.e. total binary mass and mass ratio) and similarly for the detection rates for sources with the Advanced LIGO horizon (Figure 9). The distributions are sensitive to the BH mass function exponent. The highest possible BH mass in GN affects the total mass and mass ratio distribution just by a rescaling of the mass unit (Equation 68), but the mass-distribution of merger rates are otherwise insensitive to the maximum BH mass in GN. In particular, for mass functions steeper/shallower than $dN/dm \propto m^{-1.5}$ lead to the merger rate density to be dominated by the lowest/highest mass components in the cluster. However, the detection rate distribution is

¹⁸ Eccentric BH binaries form through GW capture in GN with initial dimensionless pericenter distance $\rho_{p0} = r_{p0}/M_{\text{tot}} \lesssim 80$ ($\rho_{p0} \lesssim 100$) for masses $30M_{\odot} - 30M_{\odot}$ ($10M_{\odot} - 10M_{\odot}$) mass, see Figure 4.

skewed towards higher masses due to the higher sensitivity of Advanced LIGO/VIRGO to heavier BHs for mass function exponents shallower than $dN/dm \propto m^{-3}$.

- (x) We calculated the value of the universal dimensionless parameter $\alpha = -M_{\text{tot}} \partial^2 \ln \mathcal{R} / \partial m_A \partial m_B$ which characterizes the physical origin of a source population independently of the underlying BH mass function (Kocsis et al. 2017). We found that for GW capture sources in a mass segregated cusp, it follows a monotonically decreasing function of total binary mass (Equation 67) ranging between $1.43 \geq \alpha \geq -26.1 + (\Lambda^{3/28} - \Lambda^{-3/28})^{-1} \ln^2 \Lambda$, where $\ln \Lambda$ is the Coulomb logarithm. For $\ln \Lambda \sim 7$, this parameter is approximately $\alpha \sim -5.5$ and 1.4 for the heaviest and lightest components, respectively. This is very different from α of other GW source populations, since $\alpha \sim 4$ for BH mergers in globular clusters (O’Leary et al. 2016), $\alpha = 1$ for primordial BH binaries formed in the early universe (Kocsis et al. 2017), and $\alpha = 1.43$ for BH binaries that form due to GW capture in otherwise dynamically collisionless systems such as black holes in dark matter halos (Bird et al. 2016).
- (xi) The mass ratio distribution is wide, for mass functions $dN/dm \propto m^{-1}$ to $dN/dm \propto m^{-3}$ (Figure 10). For these mass functions, the detection of equal mass mergers are highly disfavored for low mass BHs, but equal mass mergers are possible among high BH mass sources. Unequal mass mergers are possible for a wider range of total masses (Figure 9).
- (xii) The mass distributions of mergers and the total rate per galaxy are not sensitive to the mass of the central SMBH mass. This implies that dwarf galaxies may dominate the merger rates for GW capture sources.
- (xiii) Since GW capture sources are formed roughly independently of BH spins and spin directions at pericenter distances exceeding a few tens of M_{tot} , the spin direction distribution for these sources is expected to be isotropic.

In conclusion, the measurement of the parameter distribution of merging compact objects may be useful to distinguish this formation mechanism from other mechanisms. Search methods targeting EBBH sources forming through GW capture in GN hosts may be optimized for the predicted distribution of binary parameters.

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APPENDIX

A. THE REGION OF EBBH FORMATION INSIDE THE GALACTIC NUCLEUS

The PDF of ϵ_0 and ρ_{p0} is sensitive to the value of the innermost radius $r_{\text{min}}^{A,B}$ where BHs may reside. We determine $r_{\text{min}}^{A,B}$

here, using the following assumptions:

- (A) $t_{\text{rlx}} \leq t_{\text{H}}$ the system reaches collisional equilibrium, i.e. the number density profiles of stellar populations (e.g. WDs, MSs, NS, and BHs) relax into a mass-segregated steady state power-law density cusp within a Hubble time $t_{\text{H}} = 10^{10}$ yr;
- (B) $t_{\text{rlx}} \leq t_{\text{GW}}$ the relaxation time of BHs t_{rlx} is equal or less than the infall of a BH into the SMBH t_{GW} .

We discuss the implications of these criteria in separate subsections next.

A.1. Criterion A, $t_{\text{rlx}} \leq t_{\text{H}}$

We assume the GN to be relaxed if all of its stellar components (e.g. WDs, MSs, NSs, and BHs) are relaxed within the age of the galaxy, t_{H} . The evolution of the number density distribution of stellar populations is governed by the Fokker-Plank equation which describes the energy and angular momentum diffusion and dynamical friction due to two-body interactions among all objects in the system (Bahcall & Wolf 1976, 1977; Freitag et al. 2006; Hopman & Alexander 2006; Alexander & Hopman 2009; O’Leary et al. 2009). For each stellar component of mass m , we use the local Chandrasekhar two-body energy relaxation time to reach steady state (Alexander & Livio 2004; O’Leary et al. 2009; Alexander & Pfuhl 2014)

$$t_{\text{rlx}}(r, m, M_{\text{SMBH}}) = 0.34 \frac{\sigma_*^3(r)}{G^2 n_{\text{tot}}(r) \langle M^2 \rangle \ln \Lambda} \quad (\text{A1})$$

(Spitzer 1987). Here $\sigma_*(r)$ denotes the 1D velocity dispersion, which is of the form

$$\sigma_*^2(r) = \frac{v_{\text{circ}}^2}{1 + \alpha(m)} \quad (\text{A2})$$

(Alexander 1999; Alexander & Pfuhl 2014), where v_{circ} denotes the circular velocity at radius r ¹⁹, and $\alpha(m)$ is the exponent of the number density distribution of mass m objects surrounding the SMBH²⁰. The Coulomb logarithm $\ln \Lambda$ in Equation (A1) can be approximated as $\Lambda \sim M_{\text{SMBH}}/m$ in the region where the gravitational force is dominated by the central SMBH (i.e. when $r_{\text{G}} \leq r \leq r_{\text{max}}$) (Bar-Or et al. 2013). $\langle M^2 \rangle$ in Equation (A1) is the second moment of the mass-function for the mixture of stellar populations at each radius:

$$\langle M^2 \rangle(r) = n(m, r)^{-1} \int dm n(m, r) m^2, \quad (\text{A3})$$

where $n(m, r)$ denotes the number density distribution of mass m objects. Thus, $\langle M^2 \rangle$ can be given for the mixture of the WD, MS, NS, and BH populations. In this paper we carry out our calculations separately for an idealized single-mass BH population and for a multi-mass population. For the single-mass case, we have

$$n_{\text{tot}}(r) \langle M^2 \rangle(r) = n_{\text{MS}}(r) m_{\text{MS}}^2 + n_{\text{WD}}(r) m_{\text{WD}}^2 + n_{\text{NS}}(r) m_{\text{NS}}^2 + n_{\text{BH},s}(r) m_{\text{BH}}^2, \quad (\text{A4})$$

and for the general multi-mass BH population

$$n_{\text{tot}}(r) \langle M^2 \rangle(r) = n_{\text{MS}}(r) m_{\text{MS}}^2 + n_{\text{WD}}(r) m_{\text{WD}}^2 + n_{\text{NS}}(r) m_{\text{NS}}^2 + \int_{m_{\text{BH},\text{min}}}^{m_{\text{BH},\text{max}}} dm_{\text{BH}} n_{\text{BH},m}(r, m_{\text{BH}}) m_{\text{BH}}^2, \quad (\text{A5})$$

¹⁹ $v_{\text{circ}} = \sqrt{GM_{\text{SMBH}}/r}$

²⁰ α is given for the considered stellar populations in Section 2.2.

where n_{MS} , n_{WD} , n_{NS} , and $n_{\text{BH},s,m}$ are given in Section 2.2. We look for the solution to Criterion (A) in the range of radii between the gravitational radius of the central SMBH ($r_{\text{GR}} = 2GM_{\text{SMBH}}/c^2$) and the radius of influence r_{max} .

We find numerically that t_{rlx} increases with r , m , and M_{SMBH} . Since $r < r_{\text{max}}$ and $m \leq m_{\text{BH},\text{max}}$, we find that Criterion (A) may only be satisfied if $M_{\text{SMBH}} \lesssim 10^7 M_{\odot}$ for all multi-mass BH parameters considered. A more detailed analysis by Bar-Or et al. (2013) reached a similar conclusion. We restrict the range of SMBH mass to $M_{\text{SMBH}} \leq 10^7 M_{\odot}$.

A.2. Criterion B, $t_{\text{rlx}} \leq t_{\text{GW}}$

We use Peters (1964) to calculate the evolution of the semi-major axis for an eccentric orbit

$$t_{\text{GW}}(a, m, M_{\text{SMBH}}, e) = \frac{1}{a} \left(\frac{da}{dt} \right)^{-1} = - \frac{5c^5 a^4}{64G^3 \mu M_{\text{tot}}^2} \frac{(1-e^2)^{7/2}}{\left(1 + \frac{73}{24}e^2 + \frac{37}{96}e^4\right)}, \quad (\text{A6})$$

where now, when discussing the infall of an object of mass m into the SMBH, $M_{\text{tot}} = M_{\text{SMBH}}$ and $\mu = m$. At the boundary of Criterion (B), we set this equal to the relaxation time, where for concreteness²¹ we substitute the semi-major axis in Equation (A1). Note that this refers to two-body relaxation which governs the evolution of the semi-major axis. The eccentricity distribution relaxes faster due to coherent gravitational torques arising between elliptical orbits, on the so-called resonant relaxation timescale (Rauch & Tremaine 1996; Kocsis & Tremaine 2011).

The GW inspiral timescale t_{GW} is smaller for more massive objects or for higher orbital eccentricity around the SMBH for a fixed semi-major axis. This leads to the preferential removal of the more massive BHs and the more eccentric orbits for a fixed semi-major axis, creating a loss-cone around the SMBH. However, resonant relaxation tends to mix the eccentricity distribution of orbits around the SMBH towards an isotropic thermal distribution where $dN/de \propto e$. For such a distribution 81% of the orbits have $e < 0.9$, and 90% have $e < 0.95$.

To simply account for these effects, we calculate the $r_{\text{rlx},\text{GW}}$ radius for each BH mass m_{BH} at which Criterion (B) is satisfied in two ways. We set the eccentricity in Equation (A6) either to zero or to $e = 0.9$. These results set upper and lower bounds on $r_{\text{rlx},\text{GW}}$ for at least 81% of the population. However, since resonant relaxation is neglected in this calculation, the result for $r_{\text{rlx},\text{GW}}$ using this estimate is larger than its true value for eccentric orbits. We refer the reader to Bar-Or & Alexander (2016) a detailed analysis. For a Milky Way-size nucleus (Figure 11), we find that for $e = 0$ ($e = 0.9$), $t_{\text{rlx}} \leq t_{\text{GW}}$ is satisfied at $r \gtrsim 260 M_{\text{SgrA}^*}$ ($r \gtrsim 1980 M_{\text{SgrA}^*}$) for $M = 5 M_{\odot}$ and $r \gtrsim 460 M_{\text{SgrA}^*}$ ($r \gtrsim 3220 M_{\text{SgrA}^*}$) for $M = 30 M_{\odot}$, respectively. The boundary varies monotonically with the mass of the objects and e . In the following, we adopt the cutoff radii

$$r_{\text{min}}(m_{\text{BH}}) = r_{\text{circ}}^{\text{rlx},\text{GW}}(m_{\text{BH}}), \quad (\text{A7})$$

which corresponds to circular orbits. We assume that at $r > r_{\text{min}}$, the objects which are removed by the SMBH due to GW emission are continuously replenished from the outside due to

²¹ The results are not sensitive to this assumption, since the relaxation time is very weakly sensitive to radius, $t_{\text{rlx}} \propto r^{\alpha-1.5}$.

Figure 11. The radius $r^{\text{rx,GW}}$ at which the GW inspiral timescale equals the 2-body relaxation time as a function of the mass of the object orbiting around the SMBH. The two curves correspond to different eccentricities: $e = 0$ (lower curve) and 0.9 (upper curve). Both lines correspond to BHs forming in a fiducial multi-mass BH population with $dN/dm \propto m^{-2.35}$, $m_{\text{BH,max}} = 30 M_{\odot}$, and $p_0 = 0.5$. The two symbols correspond to $r^{\text{rx,GW}}$ for a single mass BH population with $10 M_{\odot}$ (star for $e_0 = 0$, cross for $e_0 = 0.9$). We considered a Milky Way-size nucleus here.

relaxation to maintain a steady state density. The innermost radius of the GN at which BHs with masses m_A and m_B can form EBBHs is defined as

$$r_{\text{min}}^{A,B} = \max(r_{\text{min}}(m_A), r_{\text{min}}(m_B)). \quad (\text{A8})$$

We note that this minimum radius is weakly sensitive to the parameters of the multi-mass BH population.

The results for r_{min} are robust, they are weakly sensitive to the assumptions on the stellar cluster. For a multi-mass MS population with a power-law PMF $m_{\text{MS}}^{2.35}$, a highest possible stellar mass of $10 M_{\odot}$ ²² and radial density exponent $\alpha_{\text{MS}} = 1.4$, we find that r_{min} and thus $r_{\text{min}}^{A,B}$ slightly ($\leq 15\%$) differs from that calculated for a single-mass MS population.

B. ANALYTIC ESTIMATES OF MERGER RATE DISTRIBUTIONS

In this Appendix, we derive the EBBH merger rate distributions in a single GN analytically without resorting to Monte Carlo techniques. Generally, the scattering rates of objects of two masses m_A and m_B are proportional to $n_A n_B \sigma w$, where $n_{A,B}$ are the corresponding number densities, σ is the cross section to form an EBBH in a close encounter. The latter depends on the magnitude of relative velocity $w = |\mathbf{v}_A - \mathbf{v}_B|$ and impact parameter b . We organize the derivation as follows. First, we define the phase space distribution function assuming an isotropic distribution in Appendix B.1. In Appendix B.2, we derive the relative velocity distribution. In Appendix B.3, we calculate the radial distribution of GW capture and collision rates. In Appendices B.4, B.5, and B.6, we derive the EBBH merger rate distribution as a function of initial binary parameters, including the two-dimensional merger rate distribution in the $\epsilon_0 - r_{p0}$ plane, and the marginalized 1D merger rate distribution as a function of r_{p0} and ϵ_0 , respectively. In Appendix B.7, we determine the total mass and mass ratio dependent merger rate distributions, and the merger rate dis-

²² This assumption is consistent with most of the supersolar mass stars in the Galactic center with lifetimes higher than 10^7 yr (Bartko et al. 2010), and we neglect the dynamical contributions of shorter lived massive stars. The results are not sensitive to this assumption.

tribution of other component-mass dependent variables (e.g. chirp mass, mass ratio, total mass, reduced mass, and symmetric mass ratio).

B.1. Relative velocities in galactic nuclei

In this paper, we consider an approximately spherical (isotropic) distribution of compact objects around a SMBH. The equilibrium one-body phase space distribution of objects can be given by the Bahcall-Wolf model (Bahcall & Wolf 1976, 1977; Keshet et al. 2009) as

$$f(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{v}, m) = C(m) E(r, v)^{p(m)}, \quad (\text{B1})$$

where the $C(m)$ normalization constant and $p(m)$ exponent depend on the mass of the component as shown in Equation (5) and E is the binding energy per unit mass:

$$E(r, v) = \frac{M_{\text{SMBH}}}{r} - \frac{v^2}{2}. \quad (\text{B2})$$

Equation (B1) is valid outside the “loss cone” (Shapiro & Lightman 1976; Syer & Ulmer 1999), where objects are not removed by the SMBH and interior to the radius of influence of the SMBH. We approximate this region with $r_{\text{min}} \leq r \leq r_{\text{max}}$ and $0 \leq v \leq v_{\text{max}}(r)$, where r_{min} is defined to be the inner radius inside the GN at which the density cusp of BHs exhibit a cutoff (Appendix A), r_{max} is the radius of influence (Section 2.1), and $v_{\text{max}}(r)$ is the local escape velocity at radius r . The $C(m)$ normalization constant in Equation (B1) can be given by the total number of BHs at fixed mass m :

$$\frac{dN}{dm} = \int_{r_{\text{min}}(m)}^{r_{\text{max}}} dr 4\pi r^2 \int_0^{v_{\text{max}}(r)} dv 4\pi v^2 f(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{v}, m). \quad (\text{B3})$$

Let us now change the integration variable from v to $\bar{v} = v/v_{\text{max}}(r)$, where $v_{\text{max}}(r)$ is given by Equation (6). From Equations (B1)–(B3) we get that and the corresponding phase space distribution function is

$$f(r, \bar{v}, m) = C(m) n(r, m) \varphi(\bar{v}, m), \quad (\text{B4})$$

where

$$n(r, m) \equiv r^{-\alpha(m)} \quad \text{and} \quad \varphi(\bar{v}, m) \equiv (1 - \bar{v}^2)^{p(m)}, \quad (\text{B5})$$

if $r_{\text{min}} \leq r \leq r_{\text{max}}$, and if $0 \leq \bar{v} \leq 1$. The α_m exponent in Equation (B5) satisfies

$$\alpha(m) = \frac{3}{2} + p(m) = \frac{3}{2} + p_0 \frac{m}{m_{\text{BH,max}}}, \quad (\text{B6})$$

where we have used Equation (5) and we set $p_0 = 0.5$. Thus $C(m)$ can be expressed in Equation (B4) as

$$C(m) = N \mathcal{F}(m) C_r(m) C_{\bar{v}}(m), \quad (\text{B7})$$

where N is the total number of BHs in the GN (Equation 13), $\mathcal{F}(m)$ is the BH mass function with unit integral (Equation 16), $C_r(m)$ and $C_{\bar{v}}(m)$ are normalization constants defined such that $C_r(m)n(r, m)$ and $C_{\bar{v}}(m)\varphi(\bar{v}, m)$ have unit integrals over r and \bar{v} , respectively, for fixed m (Equation B4),

$$C_r(m) = \frac{3 - \alpha(m)}{4\pi} \frac{1}{r_{\text{max}}^{3-\alpha(m)} - r_{\text{min}}^{3-\alpha(m)}(m)}, \quad (\text{B8})$$

$$C_{\bar{v}}(m) = \frac{4^{\alpha(m)-1} \alpha(m) [2\alpha(m) - 1] \Gamma^2[\alpha(m)]}{\pi^2 \Gamma[2\alpha(m)]}. \quad (\text{B9})$$

Here, Γ is the Euler Gamma function. We utilize the distribution function in Equation (B4) next.

B.2. Relative velocity distribution

Here we derive the distribution function of the magnitude of relative velocity, w of two types of objects A and B with fixed mass m_A and m_B , respectively. Let us denote the 3-dimensional individual velocity distributions by $f_A(\mathbf{v}_A)$ and $f_B(\mathbf{v}_B)$, meaning that the number of objects in a volume element d^3v_i around \mathbf{v}_i is $dN_i = f(\mathbf{v}_i)d^3v_i$ for $i = A$ or B . The two-body velocity space is 6-dimensional. We assume that both velocity vectors have isotropic distributions. The distribution of the magnitude of relative velocity is defined as

$$F_{AB}(w) = \int d^3v_A f_A(\mathbf{v}_A) \int d^3v_B f_B(\mathbf{v}_B) \delta(w - |\mathbf{v}_A - \mathbf{v}_B|), \quad (\text{B10})$$

where $\delta(\cdot)$ is the Dirac- δ function. We simplify this equation in the following.

Let us adopt an arbitrarily oriented spherical coordinate system for the \mathbf{v}_A integral, while for the \mathbf{v}_B integral let us measure angles relative to \mathbf{v}_A . That is, we adopt (θ_B, ϕ_B) spherical coordinates in which the $\theta_B = 0$ axis is oriented along \mathbf{v}_A , while (θ_B, ϕ_B) defines \mathbf{v}_B . The θ_A , ϕ_A , and ϕ_B integrals in Equation (B10) can be independently evaluated since the integrand does not depend on these variables. We carry out the θ_B integral by changing to the variable $z = \cos(\theta_B)$ as

$$F_{AB}(w) = 16\pi^2 \int_0^\infty dv_A v_A^2 f_B(\mathbf{v}_A) \int_0^\infty dv_B v_B^2 f_A(\mathbf{v}_B) \times \frac{1}{2} \int_{-1}^1 dz \delta(w - \sqrt{v_A^2 + v_B^2 - 2v_A v_B z}). \quad (\text{B11})$$

We denote the last line by Φ , and evaluate it using the identities of the δ -function

$$\begin{aligned} \int_I f(x) \delta(x) dx &= \begin{cases} f(0) & \text{if } 0 \in I \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \\ &= \int_J x'(z) f[x(z)] \delta[x(z)] dz \\ &= \int_J g(z) \delta[x(z)] dz \\ &= \begin{cases} g(z_0)/x'(z_0) & \text{if } z_0 \in J \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \end{aligned} \quad (\text{B12})$$

where $x(z)$ is an arbitrary monotonic differentiable function, $g(z) = x'(z)f[x(z)]$, where $x'(z) = dx/dz$, z_0 and J are defined by $x(z_0) = 0$ and $x[J] = I$. For $g(z) = 1$ and $x(z) = w - \sqrt{v_A^2 + v_B^2 - 2v_A v_B z}$, we get

$$\Phi = \frac{w}{v_A v_B} \times \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } |\mathbf{v}_A - \mathbf{v}_B| \leq w \leq |\mathbf{v}_A + \mathbf{v}_B| \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}. \quad (\text{B13})$$

Substituting in Equation (B11), the support of the integral is the region for which $|\mathbf{v}_A - \mathbf{v}_B| \leq w \leq |\mathbf{v}_A + \mathbf{v}_B|$, $0 \leq v_A \leq v_A^{\max}$ and $0 \leq v_B \leq v_B^{\max}$, thus we find

$$F_{AB}(w) = 8\pi^2 w \int_0^{\min(v_A^{\max}, v_B^{\max} + w)} dv_A v_A f_A(v_A) \times \int_{\min(1, |\bar{v}_A - \bar{w}|)}^{\min(v_B^{\max}, v_A^{\max} + w)} dv_B v_B f_B(v_B). \quad (\text{B14})$$

Now we consider the case where $f_A(\cdot) = f_B(\cdot)$. Let us switch to the dimensionless velocity variables $\bar{v}_i = v_i/v_{\max}(r)$, and to

the dimensionless relative velocity $\bar{w} = w/v_{\max}(r)$ ($0 \leq \bar{w} \leq 2$), where $v_{\max}(r)$ is the local escape velocity at radius r given by Equation (6). The distribution of \bar{w} , $F_{AB}(\bar{w})$, can be obtained by the equation $F_{AB}(w)dw = F_{AB}(\bar{w})d\bar{w}$, which gives

$$F_{AB}(\bar{w}) = 8\pi^2 \bar{w} \int_0^1 d\bar{v}_A \bar{v}_A f(\bar{v}_A) \int_{\min(1, |\bar{v}_A - \bar{w}|)}^{\min(1, \bar{v}_A + \bar{w})} d\bar{v}_B \bar{v}_B f(\bar{v}_B). \quad (\text{B15})$$

For the phase space distribution function of relaxed galactic nuclei, Equation (B4), the integral over $d\bar{v}_B$ can be evaluated analytically, which yields

$$F_{AB}(\bar{w}) = \frac{4\pi^2 \bar{w}}{p_B + 1} \times \int_{\bar{w}-1}^1 d\bar{v}_A \bar{v}_A (1 - \bar{v}_A^2)^{p_A} [1 - (\bar{v}_A - \bar{w})^2]^{p_B + 1}. \quad (\text{B16})$$

The remaining integral over \bar{v}_A can also be evaluated analytically for any integer or half-integer p_A and p_B . In particular, for $p_A = p_B = 0$, $\alpha_A = \alpha_B = 3/2$, $F_{AB}(\bar{w}) = \frac{1}{3}\pi^2 \bar{w}^2 (2 - \bar{w})^2 (\bar{w} + 4)$. Note that $\alpha = 7/4$ for the equilibrium distribution for single-mass clusters (Bahcall & Wolf 1976) and $1.5 < \alpha < 3$ for multi-mass mass-segregated models (Keshet et al. 2009).

B.3. GW capture and collision rates for fixed component masses

We consider the merger rates between two types of objects A and B with masses m_A and m_B , drawn from phase space distribution given by Equation (B1). The differential rate of merger among two types of objects A with phase space distributions $f_A(\mathbf{r}_A, \mathbf{v}_A)$ at location (r_A, v_A) in a phase space volume $d^3r_A d^3v_A$ and similarly for objects B , is

$$d^{12}\Gamma_{AB} = \sigma w f_A(\mathbf{r}_A, \mathbf{v}_A) f_B(\mathbf{r}_B, \mathbf{v}_B) d^3r_A d^3r_B d^3v_A d^3v_B, \quad (\text{B17})$$

where $\sigma \equiv \sigma(w)$ is the GW capture cross section. We consider the formation of EBBHs in the radius range of $[r_{\min}^{A,B}, r_{\max}]$.

We consider the case of GW capture and direct collision events. Here ‘‘GW capture’’ refers to events where initially unbound black holes (i.e. asymptotically nonzero kinetic energy at infinite separation) are captured into a bounded system due to GW emission or if they suffer a direct collision. ‘‘Direct collision’’ refers to the case in which the impact parameter is sufficiently small such that the BHs collide directly in less than one orbit. In order to get captured into an eccentric binary with multiple orbits before merger the impact parameter must be in the range $b_{\min}(w) < b < b_{\max}(w)$ given by Equation (26). The cross section to form such a binary may be written as $\sigma(w) = \pi b_{\max}^2(w) - \pi b_{\min}^2(w)$. From Equation (26) we find that the encounter rate for this event can be expressed as

$$\sigma w = [\zeta_{\text{capt}}(r) \xi_{\text{capt}}(\bar{w}) - \zeta_{\text{coll}}(r) \xi_{\text{coll}}(\bar{w})] \delta(r_A - r) \delta(r_B - r), \quad (\text{B18})$$

where the δ -functions ensure that bounded systems can form only when $\mathbf{r}_A \approx \mathbf{r}_B = r$ for any r (‘‘short-range encounters’’) and we introduced

$$\zeta_{\text{capt}}(r) = \pi c_\eta^{2/7} M_{\text{tot}}^2 v_{\max}^{-11/7}(r), \quad \xi_{\text{capt}}(\bar{w}) = \bar{w}^{-11/7}, \quad (\text{B19})$$

$$\zeta_{\text{coll}}(r) = 16\pi M_{\text{tot}}^2 v_{\max}^{-1}(r), \quad \xi_{\text{coll}}(\bar{w}) = \bar{w}^{-1}, \quad (\text{B20})$$

and where

$$c_\eta = \frac{340\pi}{3} \eta. \quad (\text{B21})$$

The rate of eccentric inspirals is the difference of capture and direct collision rates. In the following we evaluate the merger rates of capture sources and direct collisions separately using the corresponding ζ and ξ functions in Equations (B19) and (B20). Substituting into Equations (B17) the differential rate of mergers in a spherical shell of volume $d^3r_{A,B} = 4\pi r^2 dr$ with $r = |\mathbf{r}_A| \approx |\mathbf{r}_B|$ with velocities v_A and v_B is

$$d^7\Gamma_{AB} = 4\pi r^2 \zeta(r) \xi(\bar{w}) f_A(r, \mathbf{v}_A) f_B(r, \mathbf{v}_B) dr d^3v_A d^3v_B. \quad (\text{B22})$$

The GW capture process depends on v_A and v_B only through the combination $w = |v_A - v_B|$, allowing us to make further simplifications. The merger rate distribution as a function of w may be derived by multiplying $d^7\Gamma_{AB}$ by $\delta(w - |\mathbf{v}_A - \mathbf{v}_B|)$ and integrating over d^3v_A and d^3v_B . Substituting Equation (B4), we get

$$\begin{aligned} \left\langle \frac{\partial^4 \Gamma}{\partial r \partial w \partial m_A \partial m_B} \right\rangle_{\mathbf{v}_A, \mathbf{v}_B} &= 4\pi r^2 \zeta(r) \xi(\bar{w}) n_A(r) n_B(r) C_A C_B \\ &\times \int d^3v_A \varphi_A(\bar{v}_A) \int d^3v_B \varphi_B(\bar{v}_B) \\ &\times \delta(w - |\mathbf{v}_A - \mathbf{v}_B|). \end{aligned} \quad (\text{B23})$$

Using the results of Appendices B.2, this is

$$\begin{aligned} \left\langle \frac{\partial^4 \Gamma}{\partial r \partial \bar{w} \partial m_A \partial m_B} \right\rangle_{\mathbf{v}_A, \mathbf{v}_B} &= 4\pi r^2 \zeta(r) \xi(\bar{w}) \\ &\times C_A C_B n_A(r) n_B(r) F_{AB}(\bar{w}), \end{aligned} \quad (\text{B24})$$

where $F_{AB}(\bar{w})$ is the dimensionless relative velocity distribution given by Equation (B16).

The total merger rate within a spherical shell of radius r for any relative velocity, can be obtained for both capture and collision events as

$$\begin{aligned} \left\langle \frac{\partial^3 \Gamma}{\partial r \partial m_A \partial m_B} \right\rangle_{\mathbf{v}_A, \mathbf{v}_B} &= 4\pi r^2 \zeta(r) C_A C_B n_A(r) n_B(r) \\ &\times \int_0^2 d\bar{w} \xi(\bar{w}) F_{AB}(\bar{w}), \end{aligned} \quad (\text{B25})$$

and the total merger rate for any encounter position is

$$\begin{aligned} \left\langle \frac{\partial^2 \Gamma}{\partial m_A \partial m_B} \right\rangle &= 4\pi C_A C_B \int_{r_{\min}^{A,B}}^{r_{\max}} dr r^2 n_A(r) n_B(r) \zeta(r) \\ &\times \int_0^2 d\bar{w} \xi(\bar{w}) F_{AB}(\bar{w}). \end{aligned} \quad (\text{B26})$$

Although this result is already simple to evaluate numerically for the relative velocity distribution function in Equation (B16) for capture and direct collision sources, ζ and ξ given by Equations (B19) and (B20), we find that the result is not sensitive to the relative velocity distribution in the following sense. Following O'Leary et al. (2009) we may approximate the integral over the relative velocity distribution with the value for circular orbits,²³ $\bar{w} = v_{\text{circ}}(r)/v_{\text{max}}(r) = 2^{-1/2}$, to get

$$C_{\bar{v}_A} C_{\bar{v}_B} \int_0^2 d\bar{w} \xi(\bar{w}) F_{AB}(\bar{w}) \approx \xi(2^{-1/2}). \quad (\text{B27})$$

Here $C_{\bar{v}_{A,B}}$ are given by Equation (B9). We find that this approximation is valid up to an error less than 18% for a wide range of BH masses between $5M_\odot$ and $80M_\odot$.

²³ Here $v_{\text{circ}} = \sqrt{M_{\text{SMBH}}/r}$ is the circular velocity at radius r .

Thus, Equations (B25) and (B26) can be approximated for GW capture and collision events as

$$\left\langle \frac{\partial^3 \Gamma}{\partial r \partial m_A \partial m_B} \right\rangle \approx 4\pi r^2 N_A N_B C_{rA} C_{rB} n_A(r) n_B(r) \zeta(r) \xi(2^{-1/2}), \quad (\text{B28})$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \left\langle \frac{\partial^2 \Gamma}{\partial m_A \partial m_B} \right\rangle &\approx N_A N_B C_{rA} C_{rB} \xi(2^{-1/2}) \\ &\times \int_{r_{\min}^{A,B}}^{r_{\max}} dr 4\pi r^2 n_A(r) n_B(r) \zeta(r), \end{aligned} \quad (\text{B29})$$

where $r_{\min}^{A,B} = \max(r_{\min}^A, r_{\min}^B)$, $C_{rA,B}$ are given by Equation (B8), and $\zeta(r)$ and $\xi(\bar{w})$ are given by Equations (B19) and (B20).

B.4. Merger rate distribution in the $\epsilon_0 - r_{p0}$ plane for fixed component masses

To derive the merger rate distribution as a function of the initial orbital elements, we first calculate the merger rate distribution as a function of b , w , and r . The differential cross section for a fixed r , w , and impact parameter between b and $b+db$ is $d\sigma = 2\pi b db$. Using Equation (B25), we get

$$\begin{aligned} \left\langle \frac{\partial^5 \Gamma}{\partial r \partial b \partial w \partial m_A \partial m_B} dr db dw \right\rangle &= 4\pi r^2 C_A C_B n_A(r) n_B(r) \\ &\times 2\pi b w P_{AB}(w|r) dr db dw \end{aligned} \quad (\text{B30})$$

if $b_{\min}(w) < b < b_{\max}(w)$, and 0 otherwise. Here we have introduced the conditional PDF of w at radius r ,

$$P_{AB}(w|r) = \frac{F_{AB}[w/v_{\max}(r)]}{v_{\max}(r)}, \quad (\text{B31})$$

where $F_{AB}[w/v_{\max}(r)]$ is given by Equation (B16).

Next we change variables in Equation (B30) from (b, w) to (r_{p0}, ϵ_0) using $db dw = J dr_{p0} d\epsilon_0$, where $J = |\partial(b, w)/\partial(r_{p0}, \epsilon_0)|$ is the Jacobian. From Equations (19), (21), (42), and (46) we get that to leading order

$$r_{p0}(b, w) = \frac{b^2 w^2}{2M_{\text{tot}}}, \quad \epsilon_0(b, w) = \frac{340\pi \eta M_{\text{tot}}^5}{3b^5 w^5} - \frac{b^2 w^4}{M_{\text{tot}}^2}. \quad (\text{B32})$$

To understand how the boundaries of the regions transform, we note that $b > b_{\min}(w)$ corresponds to $r_{p0} > r_{p0,\min} = 8M_{\text{tot}}$, and $b < b_{\max}(w)$ corresponds to $\epsilon_0 > 0$, see Section 4.3 for both two conditions. Substituting in Equation (B30), the merger rate distribution as a function of r , r_{p0} , and ϵ_0 is

$$\begin{aligned} \left\langle \frac{\partial^5 \Gamma}{\partial r \partial r_{p0} \partial \epsilon_0 \partial m_A \partial m_B} \right\rangle &= 2\pi^2 M_{\text{tot}}^2 C_A C_B n_A(r) n_B(r) \\ &\times \frac{r^2 F_{AB}(\bar{w})}{r_{p0} \bar{w}^2 v_{\max}^3(r)} \end{aligned} \quad (\text{B33})$$

if $r_{p0} > 8M_{\text{tot}}$ and $\epsilon_0 > 0$, and the merger rate is zero otherwise. Here $\bar{w} \equiv w(r_{p0}, \epsilon_0)/v_{\max}(r)$, see Equation (43), $v_{\max}(r)$ is given by Equation (6), $C_{A,B}$ are given by Equations (B7)–(B9), $n_{A,B}(r)$ are given by Equations (B5) and (B6), and $F_{AB}(\bar{w})$ is given by Equation (B16).

The distribution in terms of the dimensionless pericenter distance $\rho_{p0} = r_{p0}/M_{\text{tot}}$ is

$$\left\langle \frac{\partial^5 \Gamma}{\partial r \partial \rho_{p0} \partial \epsilon_0 \partial m_A \partial m_B} \right\rangle = M_{\text{tot}} \left\langle \frac{\partial^5 \Gamma}{\partial r \partial r_{p0} \partial \epsilon_0 \partial m_A \partial m_B} \right\rangle. \quad (\text{B34})$$

The merger rate distribution in the $\epsilon_0 - \rho_{p0}$ plane can be given by integrating Equation (B33) over r ,

$$\left\langle \frac{\partial^4 \Gamma}{\partial \rho_{p0} \partial \epsilon_0 \partial m_A \partial m_B} \right\rangle = \int_{r_{\min}^{A,B}}^{r_{\max}} dr \left\langle \frac{\partial^5 \Gamma}{\partial r \partial \rho_{p0} \partial \epsilon_0 \partial m_A \partial m_B} \right\rangle. \quad (\text{B35})$$

B.5. Merger rate distribution as a function of r_{p0} for fixed component masses

The merger rate distribution as a function of r_{p0} can be obtained by integrating Equation (B33) over r and ϵ_0 . An algebraically simpler result can be derived directly from Equation (B30) by changing variables from (b, w) to (r_{p0}, w) and integrating over r and w . In this way, we avoid the variable change to ϵ_0 . Equation (42) implies that $dr_{p0} dw = w^2 b db dw / M_{\text{tot}}$. Thus,

$$\frac{\partial^5 \Gamma}{\partial r \partial r_{p0} \partial w \partial m_A \partial m_B} dr dr_{p0} dw = 8\pi^2 C_A C_B n_A(r) n_B(r) r^2 dr \times \frac{dr_{p0}}{w} M_{\text{tot}} P_{AB}(w|r) dw \quad (\text{B36})$$

if $b < b_{\max}$, where $P_{AB}(w|r)$ is given by Equations (B16) and (B31), and $\partial^5 \Gamma / \partial r \partial r_{p0} \partial w \partial m_A \partial m_B = 0$ otherwise. The condition $b < b_{\max}$ may be equivalently written as

$$r_{p0} < r_{p0, \max}(r, w) = \frac{b_{\max}^2(w) w^2}{2M_{\text{tot}}}, \quad (\text{B37})$$

where $b_{\max}(w)$ is given by Equation (26), which gives

$$\bar{w} < \bar{w}_{\max}(r_{p0}, r) \equiv (2r_{p0})^{-7/4} c_{\eta}^{1/2} v_{\max}(r)^{-1} M_{\text{tot}}^{7/4}. \quad (\text{B38})$$

Now let us substitute Equation (B31), change integration variable to $\bar{w} = w/v_{\max}(r)$ and integrate over the allowed regions:

$$\left\langle \frac{\partial^3 \Gamma}{\partial r_{p0} \partial m_A \partial m_B} \right\rangle = \int_{r_{\min}^{A,B}}^{r_{\max}} dr \frac{C_A C_B n_A(r) n_B(r) M_{\text{tot}} 8\pi^2 r^2}{v_{\max}(r)} \times \int_0^{\min[2, \bar{w}_{\max}(r_{p0}, r)]} d\bar{w} \frac{F_{AB}(\bar{w})}{\bar{w}}. \quad (\text{B39})$$

Equation (B36) is independent of r_{p0} , which shows that the merger rates are uniformly distributed in pericenter distance for a fixed r and w . The merger rate distribution integrated over r is uniform in r_{p0} for

$$r_{p0} \leq r_{p0, \text{uni}} \equiv \frac{2b_{\max}^2[2v_{\max}(r_{\min})]v_{\max}^2(r_{\min})}{M_{\text{tot}}} = \left(\frac{85\pi}{24\sqrt{2}} \right)^{2/7} M_{\text{tot}} \frac{\eta^{2/7}}{v_{\max}^{4/7}(r_{\min})}, \quad (\text{B40})$$

where $b_{\max}(\cdot)$ and $v_{\max}(\cdot)$ are given by Equations (26) and (6), respectively. For larger pericenter distances, $r_{p0} > r_{p0, \text{uni}}$, the rates $\langle \partial^3 \Gamma / \partial r_{p0} \partial m_A \partial m_B \rangle$ decrease continuously with r_{p0} because only relative velocities less than $\bar{w}_{\max}(r_{p0}, r)$ contribute to the integral over \bar{w} in Equation (B39).

The merger rate distribution as a function of the dimensionless pericenter distance is

$$\left\langle \frac{\partial^2 \Gamma}{\partial \rho_{p0} \partial m_A \partial m_B} \right\rangle = M_{\text{tot}} \left\langle \frac{\partial^2 \Gamma}{\partial r_{p0} \partial m_A \partial m_B} \right\rangle. \quad (\text{B41})$$

B.6. Merger rate distribution as a function of ϵ_0 for fixed component masses

Next, we derive the merger rate distribution as a function of ϵ_0 at fixed component masses. To do so, we may integrate $\partial^5 \Gamma / \partial r \partial r_{p0} \partial \epsilon_0 \partial m_A \partial m_B$ over $r_{\min}^{A,B} < r < r_{\max}$ and $8M_{\text{tot}} < r_{p0} < r_{p0, \max}(r)$. Alternatively, we can change variables from r_{p0} to \bar{w} using the relationship $r_{p0}(\bar{w}, \epsilon_0)$, e.g. by inverting the relative velocity $\bar{w}(r_{p0}, \epsilon_0)$ in Equation (43), and then integrate $\partial^5 \Gamma / \partial r \partial \bar{w} \partial \epsilon_0 \partial m_A \partial m_B$ over r and \bar{w} . The result is

$$\left\langle \frac{\partial^3 \Gamma}{\partial \epsilon_0 \partial m_A \partial m_B} \right\rangle = \int_{r_{\min}^{A,B}}^{r_{\max}} dr \frac{C_A C_B n_A(r) n_B(r) M_{\text{tot}} 8\pi^2 r^2}{v_{\max}(r)} \times \int_0^{\min[2, \bar{w}_{\max}(r_{p0}(\bar{w}, \epsilon_0), r)]} d\bar{w} \frac{F_{AB}(\bar{w})}{\bar{w}} \times \left(\frac{5}{2} \frac{\epsilon_0}{r_{p0}(\bar{w}, \epsilon_0)} + \frac{7\bar{w}^2 v_{\max}(r)^2}{M_{\text{tot}}} \right)^{-1}, \quad (\text{B42})$$

where \bar{w}_{\max} is given by Equation (B38), $v_{\max}(r)$ is given by Equation (6), $C_{A,B}$ are given by Equations (B7)–(B9), $n_{A,B}(r)$ are given by Equations (B5) and (B6), and $F_{AB}(\bar{w})$ is given by Equation (B16).

B.7. Merger rate distribution as a function of total mass and mass ratio

Up to now we considered the merger rates distributions for two components A and B, which may have different numbers N_A and N_B and normalization constants C_A and C_B , see Equation (B7). To derive the mass dependent merger rate distributions, assuming that both components are drawn from a BH mass function $\mathcal{F}(m)$, we set $N_A = N_{\text{BH}} \mathcal{F}(m_A) dm_A$ and similarly for N_B , where N_{BH} is the total number of BHs in the GN. This defines the mass-distribution of the event rates for the two components. Note that the mass dependence is also implicit in $\alpha(m_{A,B})$, which affects C_A , C_B , $n_A(r)$, $n_B(r)$, and $F_{AB}(r)$ in Equations (B4)–(B9) and Equation (B16). To spell out the mass dependence more explicitly, we rewrite Equation (B33) as

$$\left\langle \frac{\partial^5 \Gamma}{\partial r \partial r_{p0} \partial \epsilon_0 \partial m_A \partial m_B} \right\rangle = \frac{2\pi^2 M_{\text{tot}}^2 r^2 n(r, m_A) n(r, m_B)}{\bar{w}^2 v_{\max}^3(r) r_{p0}} \times C(m_A) C(m_B) F[\bar{w}, p(m_A), p(m_B)], \quad (\text{B43})$$

where $\bar{w} = w(r_{p0}, \epsilon_0, m_A, m_B) / v_{\max}(r)$ is given by Equation (43), $C(m_{A,B})$ are given by Equation (B7) and $n(r, m_{A,B})$ are given by Equations (B5)–(B9), where $F[\bar{w}, p(m_A), p(m_B)] \equiv F_{AB}(\bar{w})$ in Equation (B16). This shows that generally the 5-dimensional distribution in Equation (B43) is non-separable, and mass segregation causes the different mass components to follow different radial and velocity profiles.

Merger rate distributions with respect to the component masses follows directly from Equation (B26). Using the approximation in Equation (B27), we get from Equation (B26)

that

$$\begin{aligned} \left\langle \frac{\partial^2 \Gamma}{\partial m_A \partial m_B} \right\rangle &\approx N_{\text{BH}}^2 C_{rA} C_{rB} \mathcal{F}(m_A) \mathcal{F}(m_B) \\ &\times \int_{r_{\min}^{A,B}}^{r_{\max}} dr 4\pi r^2 v_{\text{circ}}(r) n_A(r) n_B(r) \\ &\times \pi \{ b_{\max}^2 [v_{\text{circ}}(r)] - b_{\min}^2 [v_{\text{circ}}(r)] \} \end{aligned} \quad (\text{B44})$$

if $m_{\text{BH},\min} \leq m_{A,B} \leq m_{\text{BH},\max}$, and 0 otherwise. Here $b_{\max}(w)$ and $b_{\min}(w)$ are given by Equation (26), where we substitute $w = v_{\text{circ}}(r) = \sqrt{M_{\text{SMBH}}/r}$.

For a power-law mass function with exponent $-\beta$ (see Equation (16)), we get

$$\left\langle \frac{\partial^2 \Gamma}{\partial m_A \partial m_B} \right\rangle = \left\langle \frac{\partial^2 \Gamma_{\text{capt}}}{\partial m_A \partial m_B} \right\rangle - \left\langle \frac{\partial^2 \Gamma_{\text{coll}}}{\partial m_A \partial m_B} \right\rangle, \quad (\text{B45})$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \left\langle \frac{\partial^2 \Gamma_{\text{capt}}}{\partial m_A \partial m_B} \right\rangle &\approx \frac{9m_{\text{BH},\max}^2 - 6p_0 m_{\text{BH},\max} M_{\text{tot}} + 4p_0^2 \mu M_{\text{tot}}}{m_{\text{BH},\max}^2 r_{\max}^{3-p_0 \frac{M_{\text{tot}}}{m_{\text{BH},\max}}}} \\ &\times \frac{M_{\text{tot}}^{2-\beta} \mu^{-\beta} (1-\beta)^2}{(m_{\text{BH},\max}^{1-\beta} - m_{\text{BH},\min}^{1-\beta})^2} \frac{N_{\text{BH}}^2 c_\eta^{2/7}}{16 M_{\text{SMBH}}^{11/14}} \\ &\times \frac{r_{\max}^{11/14-p_0 \frac{M_{\text{tot}}}{m_{\text{BH},\max}}} - r_{\min}^{11/14-p_0 \frac{M_{\text{tot}}}{m_{\text{BH},\max}}}}{11/14 - p_0 \frac{M_{\text{tot}}}{m_{\text{BH},\max}}} \end{aligned} \quad (\text{B46})$$

if $m_{\text{BH},\min} \leq m_{A,B} \leq m_{\text{BH},\max}$, and

$$\begin{aligned} \left\langle \frac{\partial^2 \Gamma_{\text{coll}}}{\partial m_A \partial m_B} \right\rangle &\approx \frac{9m_{\text{BH},\max}^2 - 6p_0 m_{\text{BH},\max} M_{\text{tot}} + 4p_0^2 \mu M_{\text{tot}}}{m_{\text{BH},\max}^2 r_{\max}^{3-p_0 \frac{M_{\text{tot}}}{m_{\text{BH},\max}}}} \\ &\times \frac{M_{\text{tot}}^{2-\beta} \mu^{-\beta} (1-\beta)^2}{(m_{\text{BH},\max}^{1-\beta} - m_{\text{BH},\min}^{1-\beta})^2} \frac{N_{\text{BH}}^2}{M_{\text{SMBH}}^{1/2}} \\ &\times \frac{r_{\max}^{1/2-p_0 \frac{M_{\text{tot}}}{m_{\text{BH},\max}}} - r_{\min}^{1/2-p_0 \frac{M_{\text{tot}}}{m_{\text{BH},\max}}}}{1/2 - p_0 \frac{M_{\text{tot}}}{m_{\text{BH},\max}}} \end{aligned} \quad (\text{B47})$$

if $m_{\text{BH},\min} \leq m_{A,B} \leq m_{\text{BH},\max}$, and the rates vanish otherwise. Here c_η depends on mass ratio as given by Equation (B21).

We find that $\langle \partial^2 \Gamma_{\text{coll}} / \partial m_A \partial m_B \rangle$, has a small ($\lesssim 10\%$) contribution to $\langle \partial^2 \Gamma / \partial m_A \partial m_B \rangle$. Using the expressions of N_{BH} and r_{\max} defined by Equations (13) and (1), and utilizing that $r_{\min} \ll r_{\max}$, implies that $\langle \partial^2 \Gamma / \partial m_A \partial m_B \rangle \propto M_{\text{SMBH}}^{3/28}$.

Given $\langle \partial^2 \Gamma / \partial m_A \partial m_B \rangle$, $\langle \partial^2 \Gamma / \partial M_{\text{tot}} \partial q \rangle$ can be obtained by changing variables from m_A and m_B to $M_{\text{tot}} = m_A + m_B$ and $q = m_A / m_B$ or conversely

$$m_A = \frac{q M_{\text{tot}}}{1+q}, \quad m_B = \frac{M_{\text{tot}}}{1+q}. \quad (\text{B48})$$

The Jacobian is $J = [\partial(m_A, m_B) / \partial(q, M_{\text{tot}})] = M_{\text{tot}}(1+q)^{-2}$ so $dm_A dm_B = M_{\text{tot}}(1+q)^{-2} dq dM_{\text{tot}}$, and so

$$\left\langle \frac{\partial^2 \Gamma}{\partial M_{\text{tot}} \partial q} \right\rangle = \frac{M_{\text{tot}}}{(1+q)^2} \left\langle \frac{\partial^2 \Gamma}{\partial m_A \partial m_B} \right\rangle \quad (\text{B49})$$

if

$$\frac{q m_{\text{BH},\min}}{1+q} < M_{\text{tot}} < \frac{m_{\text{BH},\max}}{1+q}, \quad (\text{B50})$$

Figure 12. The average relative velocity ($\langle w_{AB} \rangle_{v_A, v_B}$) with which BHs with component masses m_A and m_B form EBBHs in GNs. Different lines correspond to different component masses in a multi-mass BH population and in a single-mass BH population as in Figure 4.

and 0 otherwise. The merger rate distribution as a function of only M_{tot} or q respectively can be given by marginalizing Equation (B49) over q or M_{tot} .

Additionally, we note that $\langle \partial^2 \Gamma / \partial M_{\text{tot}} \partial \mu \rangle$ and $\langle \partial^2 \Gamma / \partial M \partial \eta \rangle$ can be given as

$$\left\langle \frac{\partial^2 \Gamma}{\partial M_{\text{tot}} \partial \mu} \right\rangle = \frac{2M_{\text{tot}}}{\sqrt{M_{\text{tot}}^2 - 4\mu M_{\text{tot}}}} \left\langle \frac{\partial^2 \Gamma}{\partial m_A \partial m_B} \right\rangle, \quad (\text{B51})$$

and as

$$\left\langle \frac{\partial^2 \Gamma}{\partial M \partial \eta} \right\rangle = \mathcal{M} \eta^{-6/5} (1-4\eta)^{-1/2} \left\langle \frac{\partial^2 \Gamma}{\partial m_A \partial m_B} \right\rangle, \quad (\text{B52})$$

in the range $m_{\text{BH},\min} \leq m_{A,B} \leq m_{\text{BH},\max}$, and 0 otherwise. It is straightforward to calculate the marginalized μ , η , and \mathcal{M} merger rate distributions from these equations.

We use these results to generate Figures 9 and 10.

B.8. Average relative velocity in a single galactic nucleus

Here we derive the average relative velocity $\langle w_{AB} \rangle_{v_A, v_B, r}$ with which objects with component masses m_A and m_B form EBBHs in GNs in order to clarify the M_{SMBH} dependence of both e_0 and ρ_{p0} discussed in Section 5.2.

Using the distribution of relative velocities at radius r from the SMBH, $P_{AB}(w|r)$, and the radial distribution of mergers $P_{AB}(r)$, Equations (B31) and (B28), we have

$$\langle w_{AB} \rangle_{v_A, v_B, r} = \int_{r_{\min}^{A,B}}^{r_{\max}} \langle w_{AB}(r) \rangle_{v_A, v_B} P_{AB}(r) dr, \quad (\text{B53})$$

where

$$\langle w_{AB}(r) \rangle_{v_A, v_B} = \int_0^{2v_{\max}(r)} w P_{AB}(w|r) dw, \quad (\text{B54})$$

is the average relative velocity with which BHs A and B form an EBBH at radius r from the central SMBH. Here $r \in [r_{\min}^{A,B}, r_{\max}]$ defined by Equations (A8) and (1), and $\langle w_{AB}(r) \rangle_{v_A, v_B}$ depends on both r and M_{SMBH} implicitly through $v_{\max}(r)$ (Equation 6). Here $P_{AB}(r)$ is given by Equations (55) and (56) for multi-mass and single-mass BH populations, respectively.

Examples for the M_{SMBH} dependence of $\langle w_{AB} \rangle_{v_A, v_B, r}$ are displayed in Figure 12. In case of a multi-mass BH population, we find that $\langle w_{AB} \rangle_{v_A, v_B, r}$ depends only on $m_{\text{BH},\max}$, which is

due to the fact that both $P_{AB}(w|r)$ and $P_{AB}(r)$ depend only on $m_{\max, \text{BH}}$ (see Sections B.1 and B.2 and Section 5), and $r_{\min}^{A,B}$ is weakly sensitive to the parameters of the multi-mass BH population (Section A). These properties of $\langle w_{AB}(r) \rangle_{v_A, v_B}$ also determine how ρ_{p0} and e_0 depend on M_{SMBH} (Figure 5) and the BH population parameters (Figure 6) through Equation (B33).

C. ALIGO DETECTION RATE DISTRIBUTION

In this Appendix, we determine the binary component mass-distribution of the total detection rate for GW capture sources in galactic nuclei corresponding to the planned aLIGO design sensitivity. We add up the merger rates for all galaxies with nuclear star clusters which host an SMBH within the detectable Universe and express the results as a function of the component masses $m_A - m_B$, $\partial^2 \mathcal{R}_{\text{aLIGO}} / \partial m_A \partial m_B$ and the total mass and mass ratio, $\partial^2 \mathcal{R}_{\text{aLIGO}} / \partial M_{\text{tot}} \partial q$. This is used to plot the right panels of Figure 9.

The detection rate distribution of EBBHs can be given using Equation (59) in O’Leary et al. (2009) by omitting the integral over the component masses m_A and m_B as

$$\frac{\partial^2 \mathcal{R}_{\text{aLIGO}}}{\partial m_A \partial m_B} = \int_{\rho_{p0, \min}}^{\rho_{p0, \max}} d\rho_{p0} \int_0^{z_{\max}} dz \frac{dV_C}{dz} \frac{1}{1+z} \frac{\partial^3 \mathcal{R}}{\partial \rho_{p0} \partial m_A \partial m_B}. \quad (\text{C1})$$

Here $\partial^3 \mathcal{R} / \partial \rho_{p0} \partial m_A \partial m_B$ is the comoving partial binary formation rate density between masses (m_A, m_B) for fixed ρ_{p0} , averaged over the number density distribution of M_{SMBH} in the Universe. Since $e_0 \sim 1$ for EBBHs forming through GW capture in GNs (Section 5.2), it is not necessary to average over the e_0 dependence in the comoving partial binary formation rate density, but the results may be well approximated by setting a single e_0 value (see below). In Equation (C1), z_{\max} is the redshift corresponding to the maximum detectable distance of EBBHs with component masses m_A and m_B and with ρ_{p0} , and dV_C/dz is the comoving volume density corresponding to the given cosmology. Generally this is defined as $4\pi d_L^3 (1+z)^{-2}$ (Eisenstein 1997).

$$\frac{dV_C}{dz} = \frac{c}{(1+z)^2 H_0} \frac{d_L^2(z)}{\sqrt{\Omega_M(1+z)^3 + \Omega_\Lambda}}, \quad (\text{C2})$$

where the luminosity distance for a flat Λ CDM cosmology, d_L , can be expressed as a function of z as

$$d_L(z) = \frac{(1+z)c}{H_0} \int_0^z \frac{dz'}{\sqrt{\Omega_M(1+z')^3 + \Omega_\Lambda}}, \quad (\text{C3})$$

where $H_0 = 68 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$ is the Hubble constant, and $\Omega_M = 0.304$ and $\Omega_\Lambda = 1 - \Omega_M = 0.696$ are the density parameters for matter and dark energy, respectively (Planck Collaboration et al. 2014a,b).²⁴ We determine $\partial^2 \mathcal{R}_{\text{aLIGO}} / \partial m_A \partial m_B$ for one aLIGO detector at design sensitivity (Abbott et al. 2016d).

In Equation (C1), we calculate z_{\max} from the maximum luminosity distance $d_L(z_{\max})$ of detection with given signal to noise ratio for aLIGO. For binaries on eccentric orbits, the

²⁴ If cosmological effects are ignored Equation (C1) reduces to

$$\frac{\partial^2 \mathcal{R}_{\text{aLIGO}}}{\partial m_A \partial m_B} = \int_{\rho_{p0, \min}}^{\rho_{p0, \max}} d\rho_{p0} \frac{\partial^3 \mathcal{R}}{\partial \rho_{p0} \partial m_A \partial m_B} \frac{4\pi d_{L, \max}^3}{3}, \quad (\text{C4})$$

where $d_{L, \max}$ is the maximum distance of aLIGO detection at a fixed signal to noise ratio, for EBBHs with component masses m_A and m_B and with ρ_{p0} .

sky position and binary orientation averaged root mean square signal-to-noise ratio for a single orthogonal arm interferometric GW instrument can be given as (O’Leary et al. 2009)

$$\left\langle \frac{S^2}{N^2} \right\rangle = \frac{48}{95} \frac{\eta M_{\text{tot}, z}^3 \rho_{p0}^2}{d_L^2} \int_{e_{\text{LSO}}}^{e_0} \sum_{n=1}^{n_{\max}(e_0)} \frac{g(n, e) s(e, e_0)}{n^2 S_h(f_n)} \frac{de}{e}, \quad (\text{C5})$$

where S_h is the one-sided noise spectral density, e_{LSO} is given by Equations (28) and (29), $M_{\text{tot}, z} = M_{\text{tot}}(1+z)$ is the redshifted total mass, and $g(n, e)$ and $s(e, e_0)$ are given by Equations (52) and (56) in O’Leary et al. (2009). In Equation (C5), f_n is the observed orbital harmonic at redshift z , i.e.

$$f_n = \frac{n(1 - e^{3/2})}{2\pi \rho_p^{3/2} M_{\text{tot}, z}}, \quad (\text{C6})$$

and we truncate n at $n_{\max}(e_0)$ (O’Leary et al. 2009; Mikóczy et al. 2012)

$$n_{\max}(e_0) = \left\lfloor 5 \frac{(1+e_0)^{1/2}}{(1-e_0)^{3/2}} \right\rfloor, \quad (\text{C7})$$

which accounts for 99% of the signal power (Turner 1977). Here the bracket $\lfloor \cdot \rfloor$ denotes the floor function. By setting the detection threshold to be $\langle S^2/N^2 \rangle = \text{SNR}_{\text{lim}}^2 = 8^2$ in Equation (C5), the maximum luminosity distance of detection as a function of $M_{\text{tot}, z}$, η , e_0 , and ρ_{p0} can be given as

$$d_L^{\max} = \sqrt{\frac{48}{95} \frac{\eta M_{\text{tot}, z}^3 \rho_{p0}^2}{\text{SNR}_{\text{lim}}^2} \int_{e_{\text{LSO}}}^{e_0} \sum_{n=1}^{n_{\max}(e_0)} \frac{g(n, e) s(e, e_0)}{n^2 S_h(f_n)} \frac{de}{e}} \quad (\text{C8})$$

(O’Leary et al. 2009). EBBHs form with $0.9 < e_0 < 0.9999$ in GNs (Section 5.2), therefore the integrand in Equation (C8) has a small scatter ($\lesssim 5\%$) over the range of e_0 for any ρ_{p0} occurred in MC simulations ($8 \leq \rho_{p0} < 1000$, see Section 5.2 for details). Here $d_L^{\max} \equiv d_L(z_{\max})$ given by Equation (C3). Furthermore d_L^{\max} depends on the redshifted masses as $M_{\text{tot}, z}$. Thus, for given m_A and m_B we calculate z_{\max} from Equations (C3) and (C8), which then yields d_L^{\max} . Here we adopt the simplifying approximation to set $e_0 = 0.99$.

In Equation (C1), $\partial^3 \mathcal{R} / \partial \rho_{p0} \partial m_A \partial m_B$ can be given by convolving $\langle \partial^3 \Gamma / \partial \rho_{p0} \partial m_A \partial m_B \rangle$ (Equations B39 and B41) with the number density of galaxies with nuclear star clusters that host an SMBH of mass M_{SMBH} , $dn_{\text{gal}}/dM_{\text{SMBH}}$.²⁵

$$\frac{\partial^3 \mathcal{R}}{\partial \rho_{p0} \partial m_A \partial m_B} = \int_{10^5 M_\odot}^{10^7 M_\odot} dM_{\text{SMBH}} \frac{dn_{\text{gal}}}{dM_{\text{SMBH}}} \xi \times \left\langle \frac{\partial^3 \Gamma}{\partial \rho_{p0} \partial m_A \partial m_B} \right\rangle. \quad (\text{C9})$$

Several studies provided fitting functions for the number density distribution of massive SMBHs (Salucci et al. 1999; Aller & Richstone 2002; Marconi et al. 2004; Shankar et al. 2004; Benson et al. 2007; Graham et al. 2007; Shankar et al. 2009; Vika et al. 2009; Sijacki et al. 2015), however most of them are valid for $M_{\text{SMBH}} \gtrsim 10^6 M_\odot$. In this paper the SMBH

²⁵ Here note when using Equations (B39) and (B41) and averaging over all galaxies within the aLIGO range, the detection rate is proportional to $\langle \partial^3 \Gamma / \partial \rho_{p0} \partial m_A \partial m_B \rangle \propto \langle n_A n_B \rangle \propto \langle C_A C_B n_{\text{MS}}^2 \rangle$, which may be much larger than $\langle C_A \rangle \langle C_B \rangle \langle n_{\text{MS}} \rangle^2$ due to the Cauchy-Schwarz inequality. This enhancement factor $\xi = \langle n_{\text{MS}}^2 \rangle / \langle n_{\text{MS}} \rangle^2$ was introduced in O’Leary et al. (2009). However, this quantity shifts the detection rates uniformly for different BH masses. Such constant normalization factors drop out in Figure 9.

mass range of interest is $10^5 M_\odot - 10^7 M_\odot$ (Section 2.1), we therefore interpolate the results of [Aller & Richstone \(2002\)](#), who found the best fit number density distribution of massive SMBHs to be

$$\frac{dn_{\text{gal}}}{dM_{\text{SMBH}}} = c_0 \left(\frac{M_{\text{SMBH}}}{M_*} \right)^{-1.25} \exp(-M_{\text{SMBH}}/M_*) \quad (\text{C10})$$

in the SMBH mass range of $10^4 M_\odot - 10^9 M_\odot$. In Equation (C10), $M_* = 1.3 \times 10^8 M_\odot$, and $c_0 = 3.2 \times 10^{-11} M_\odot^{-1} \text{Mpc}^{-3}$.

In Equation (C1), we set $\rho_{\text{p0,min}} = 8$ and $\rho_{\text{p0,max}} = 1000$ which captures most of the mergers for the considered ranges of SMBH mass, BH mass, and BH population parameters (Section 5.2).

Using Equation (B49), the total mass and mass ratio dependent rates may be calculated as

$$\frac{\partial^2 \mathcal{R}_{\text{aLIGO}}}{\partial M_{\text{tot}} \partial q} = \frac{M_{\text{tot}}}{(1+q)^2} \frac{\partial^2 \mathcal{R}_{\text{aLIGO}}}{\partial m_A \partial m_B} \quad (\text{C11})$$

if

$$\frac{q m_{\text{BH,min}}}{1+q} < M_{\text{tot}} < \frac{m_{\text{BH,max}}}{1+q}, \quad (\text{C12})$$

and 0 otherwise. The 1D distribution of aLIGO detection rate as a function of either M_{tot} or q can be given by marginalizing Equation (C11) over the other parameter.

Similarly to Equations (B51) and (B52), the functions $\partial^2 \mathcal{R}_{\text{aLIGO}} / \partial M_{\text{tot}} \partial \mu$ and $\partial^2 \mathcal{R}_{\text{aLIGO}} / \partial \mathcal{M} \partial \eta$ can be given as

$$\frac{\partial^2 \mathcal{R}_{\text{aLIGO}}}{\partial M_{\text{tot}} \partial \mu} = \frac{2M_{\text{tot}}}{\sqrt{M_{\text{tot}}^2 - 4\mu M_{\text{tot}}}} \frac{\partial^2 \mathcal{R}_{\text{aLIGO}}}{\partial m_A \partial m_B}, \quad (\text{C13})$$

and as

$$\frac{\partial^2 \mathcal{R}_{\text{aLIGO}}}{\partial \mathcal{M} \partial \eta} = \mathcal{M} \eta^{-6/5} (1-4\eta)^{-1/2} \frac{\partial^2 \mathcal{R}_{\text{aLIGO}}}{\partial m_A \partial m_B}, \quad (\text{C14})$$

in the range $m_{\text{BH,min}} \leq m_{A,B} \leq m_{\text{BH,max}}$, and 0 otherwise. It is straightforward to calculate the marginalized μ , η , and \mathcal{M} detection rate distributions from these equations.

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